

Childhood Cancer Survivors & their Parents

Long-Term Implications for Care

Cumulative PhD thesis

Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Christen S, Tinner EM, Kuehni CE, Gumy-Pause, F & Michel G.

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain attendance to follow-up care of childhood cancer survivors? *Psycho-Oncology*. 2018; **27**(6), 1501-1508. doi: [10.1002/pon.4680](https://doi.org/10.1002/pon.4680)

Published: 22.02.2018

Access: <https://zenodo.org/record/2385854#.YAA7Dmg-70>

Baenziger J, Hetherington K, Wakefield CE, McGill BC, Carlson L, Cohn RJ, Michel, G, & Sansom-Daly U.

Understanding parents' communication experiences in childhood cancer: A qualitative exploration and model for future research. *Supportive Care in Cancer*. 2020; **28**, 4467-4476. doi:[10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6)

Published: 11.01.2020

Access: <https://zenodo.org/record/4153557#.YAA4Tmg-70>

Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Harju, E, Ansari, M, Waespe, N, Scheineman, K, & Michel G.

Post-traumatic stress in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors and parents of the Swiss general population. *Journal of Psychosocial Oncology: Research and Practice*. 2020; **2**(3), e024. doi: [10.1097/OR9.000000000000024](https://doi.org/10.1097/OR9.000000000000024)

Published: 28.07.2020.

Access: <https://zenodo.org/record/4134526#.YAA5zmg-70>

Submitted for the degree of Doctor of Science from the Department of Health Sciences & Medicine
University of Lucerne, Switzerland

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Wolfhalden AR

10-209-419

Submitted to reviewers on Friday, 3rd April 2020, Luzern

Submitted to the department on Monday, 3rd August 2020, Luzern

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Father of 25-year old childhood cancer survivor (male, 10 years at diagnosis)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First and foremost, I would like to express my enormous gratitude to Prof Dr Gisela Michel, supervisor of the present PhD thesis and outstanding role model for women in research. I feel incredibly blessed to have found my way into her research group at the University of Lucerne in this early stage of my scientific career!

Special thank you also goes out to the secondary reviewer of the present thesis, Prof Dr med Nicolas von der Weid, and the members of the doctoral committee, Dr Katharina Roser and Prof Dr med Katrin Scheinemann, who have supported me throughout the thesis with their wisdom and encouragement.

Furthermore, I am incredibly grateful for the extremely precious support of Prof Dr Claire Wakefield and Dr Ursula Sansom-Daly, as well as their extended team during my visiting fellowship at the Behavioural Sciences Unit, Kids Cancer Centre at the Sydney Children's Hospital in Australia. Accordingly, many thanks to the Swiss National Science Foundation for awarding me the doc.mobility fellowship to make such an experience possible.

I would also like to extend an especially warm thank you to Dr Luzius Mader, who was a brilliant mentor and role model in the early phases of my PhD. And of course, last but not least, heartfelt thank you to my family and friends – who are there for me however far away I may be - physically, mentally or socially! (;

ABSTRACT

Introduction. *This thesis includes three studies addressing current research gaps in childhood cancer.*

Study 1 (<https://zenodo.org/record/2385854#.YAAAt7Dmg-70>). Childhood cancer survivors should attend long-term follow-up care to monitor their health, but many do not attend. We investigated psychosocial characteristics to help explain their behaviour.

Study 2 (<https://zenodo.org/record/4153557#.YAAAt4Tmg-70>). Parents of children diagnosed with cancer encounter difficulties in childhood cancer care. Theory-driven research is needed to understand parents' communication with health-care professionals and resulting health-care experience.

Study 3 (<https://zenodo.org/record/4134526#.YAAAt5zmg-70>). The childhood cancer experience may continue to affect parents mentally. Little is known on parents post-traumatic stress symptoms when survivors are grown-up.

Population. Cohorts included: 1. Swiss childhood cancer survivors diagnosed with cancer aged <16 years and ≥5 years since diagnosis; 2. Australian parents of children aged <18 years who recently completed cancer treatment with curative intent; and 3. Swiss parents of adult survivors of childhood cancer (aged >20 years).

Methods. Survivors and parents were recruited nationwide and asked to complete for study 1 & 3. a questionnaire survey, or for study 2. a semi-structured telephone interview. We used 1. the *Theory of Planned Behavior* and *Structural Equation Modelling*, 2. *Embodied-Societal-Psychological Perspective* in health psychology and *Grounded Theory*, 3. the *Model Of Pediatric Medical Traumatic Stress* and *Multilevel Modelling* to evaluate outcomes, and identify associated characteristics.

Results. 1. Social norms in the survivors' surrounding, including parents, are driving follow-up care attendance, even if survivors are already adults. 2. Parents' communication experiences with health-care professionals shaped their trust and engagement in their child's health-care. 3. Parents of children with chronic illness, even if already adult, reported more symptoms of post-traumatic stress.

Conclusion. 1. Parents play a crucial role in the survivors' long-term follow-up care. 2. Parents' communication experiences with health-care professionals are essential to foster optimal parental and patient engagement in care. 3. Parents of children with chronic illness are at risk for increased post-traumatic stress.

Access to support services long into survivorship could facilitate the management of long-term consequences.

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DEFINITIONS

Parents. In this thesis, the term “parents” is used in the most inclusive way possible. Parents may be the biological or adoptive parents, legal guardians of the child, or identify as parents through their role as the primary caregiver. For reasons of legibility, I will use the term “parents” as a collective term throughout.

Health-care professionals. This term refers to any professional associated with the health-care delivery for children with cancer or childhood cancer survivors.

Comparisons. This term is used in this thesis to refer to any sample that childhood cancer survivors or their parents were being compared to. In some referenced studies, this may signify a comparison with a general population, with a sample of healthy children/parents of healthy children or other control groups (active or waitlist) of randomized trials.

LTFU-care. With this term I refer to long-term follow-up care (LTFU-care), including any type of care, appointment or examination provided for childhood cancer survivors after they have completed treatment with curative intent. LTFU-care might be regular or irregular consultations with health-care professionals or may also include a formal well-structured program with specialised care.

Trust can be defined as the *“learned behaviour contingent on past interactions and experiences that develops over time and is based on the belief or confidence that a promise or verbal agreement can be relied on”* [page 611].¹

Health literacy is an evolving concept and can be defined as *“the ability to obtain, read, understand and use healthcare information in order to make appropriate health decisions and follow instructions for treatment....in ways which promote and maintain good health for themselves, their families and communities.”* [WHO statement]²

Illness perception *“... is a term used to refer to the mental representations and personal ideas that people have about illness, its consequences (impact on life), the timeline (e.g. chronic vs acute), and how the illness can be controlled.”* [page 1362]³

Implementation Science *“... is the study of methods to promote the adoption and integration of evidence-based practices, interventions and policies into routine health care and public health settings. Implementation research*

plays an important role in identifying barriers to, and enablers of, effective global health programming and policymaking, and leveraging that knowledge to develop evidence-based innovations in effective delivery approaches.” [FIC statement]⁴

Translational research “... fosters the multidirectional integration of basic research, patient-oriented research, and population-based research, with the long-term aim of improving the health of the public. T₁ research expedites the movement between basic research and patient-oriented research that leads to new or improved scientific understanding or standards of care. T₂ research facilitates the movement between patient-oriented research and population-based research that leads to better patient outcomes, the implementation of best practices, and improved health status in communities. T₃ research promotes interaction between laboratory-based research and population-based research to stimulate a robust scientific understanding of human health and disease.” [page 470].⁵

The life course approach “... aims at increasing the effectiveness of interventions throughout a person’s life. It focuses on a healthy start to life and targets the needs of people at critical periods throughout their lifetime . It promotes timely investments with a high rate of return for public health and the economy by addressing the causes, not the consequences, of ill health.” [WHO statement]⁶

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 1 provides a brief general background to gain a broader understanding of childhood cancer and its associated experiences for children themselves and their parents. The aim is to provide the reader with an understanding of the current state of research in relation to the three research gaps addressed within this doctoral thesis (leading to the publication of study 1, 2 and 3).

1. CHILDHOOD CANCER

1.1 INCIDENCE

In Switzerland, the crude incidence of childhood cancer in children aged <15 years has been assessed as 13.5 cases per 100'000.³ An average of 174 new cases have been registered every year since the establishment of the *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry* (SCCR, more information in Chapter 4) in 1976 (Figure 1).¹⁻³

The reported incidence is higher for boys than girls and twice as high in the first five years of life than during early school age.³ With age, the relative incidence of types of cancers changes: embryonic tumours are most frequent in infants, leukaemia most frequent in pre-school children, and lymphoma and bone tumour in school children. CNS tumours are relatively common at all ages.^{3,4}

Figure 1. The annual number of registered cases (including diagnoses according to the *International Classification of Childhood Cancer – 3* or Langerhans cell histiocytosis) over time at the *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry* (N= 8019, Swiss and foreign residents, ages 0-14 years).

Source: Peiffer et al., 2017, p.13¹

International reports have reported an increase in cancers during childhood since the 1970s.⁵ The increase could be explained by the diagnostic practices, changes in the environmental risk factors, or represent an artefact of reduced infant mortality.⁵ Currently, there is a limited understanding of the aetiology of childhood cancer.⁵

Incidence of childhood cancer and the proportions of reported cancer diagnoses in Switzerland are comparable to European averages, the United States of America, and Australia.^{2,5} In low-income and middle-income countries, the reported incidence of childhood cancer is lower than in high-income countries; however, the estimates might not reflect the situation of the entire countries' population because cancer registries are rare, especially in rural areas.⁵

1.2 DIAGNOSIS

In current practice, professionals distinguish twelve groups of cancers according to the third edition of the *International Classification of Childhood Cancer* (ICCC-3, Table 1).^{2,5} The ICCC-3 applies the rules, nomenclature, and codes based on the *International Classification of Disease for Oncology* (ICD-O-3), which bases a diagnosis on the cancers' morphology (tissue type), topography (surface shape), and behaviour.⁵

Code	Diagnosis
I.	Leukaemias, myeloproliferative diseases, and myelodysplastic diseases
II.	Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms
III.	Central nervous system neoplasms
IV.	Neuroblastomas and other peripheral nervous cell tumours
V.	Retinoblastomas
VI.	Renal tumours
VII.	Hepatic tumours
VIII.	Malignant bone tumours
IX.	Soft tissue and other extraosseous sarcomas
X.	Germ cell tumours, trophoblastic tumours, and neoplasms of gonads
XI.	Other malignant epithelial neoplasms and malignant melanomas
XII.	Other specified and unspecified neoplasms
	Langerhans Cell Histiocytosis

Table 1. Classification of childhood cancer diagnosis according to the ICCC-3.

Source: Steliarova-Foucher², 2005; Pfeiffer et al., 2017¹

The diagnoses with the highest prevalence are leukaemia (33% of all cancers), central nervous system tumours (20%, with a large proportion of brain tumours), and lymphomas (12%).¹ Cancers evolving from embryonic tissue include neuroblastoma (7%) from neural tissue, nephroblastoma (5%) from renal tissue, hepatoblastoma (1%) from the liver, and germ cell tumours (3%).¹ Other cancers during childhood include soft tissue sarcomas (7%), malignant bone tumours (4%), and retinoblastoma (3%).¹ Sometimes children develop other malignant cancers such as melanomas, or other rare specified and unspecified tumours (3%).¹

Langerhans cell histiocytosis (LCH) has been excluded from the classification of childhood cancer.⁶ The nature of LCH, and thus classification, is a matter of debate by clinicians, and the number of cases registered is considered incomplete.⁶ Nevertheless, in Switzerland, the *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry* registers also those diagnosed with LCH as they are treated similarly. Children treated for LCH have a high incidence of late effects and poor survival.⁷

1.3 TREATMENT

Childhood cancers differ from adult cancers, not only by the affected tissue types but also by their behaviour and their response to treatment.⁸ The treatment often includes a combination of invasive therapies, such as surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy and stem cell transplantation, dependent on the cancer type and stage of progression.⁸ In more recent years, immunotherapy has been used in clinical trials to treat children and adolescents with cancer.⁸

Since every cancer diagnosis is unique, treatment plans are highly specialised and have become more and more individualised.^{9,10} Throughout the treatment phase, treatment regimens are adjusted to the cancers' and child's response to treatment.^{9,10} For instance, they may have to be altered in response to possible infections or other complications, such as severe side effects that may occur due to the toxicity of treatment.^{9,10} Treatments which have demonstrated their effectiveness have further been studied to determine a level of dose-response in order to minimise (long-term) side effects and late mortality.^{10,11}

Both the diagnosis and treatment phase usually takes place over an extended period of time depending on the type of cancer, with treatments lasting over months and years¹², and may also include relapse(s).¹¹

1.4 SURVIVAL

Over the past three decades, survival rates of childhood cancer have improved significantly, mostly in response to aggressive and new treatment strategies.¹ In high-income countries, 5-year survival rates of children diagnosed with cancer have improved steadily and now reach over 80%.^{12,13} In Switzerland, 10-year survival has been reported to be as high as 87% for children diagnosed between 2007 and 2016 (Figure 2); reflecting the improved treatment regimens for most cancers.¹⁴

Figure 2. Survival of patients in the SCCR by period of diagnosis.

Source: Peiffer et al., 2017, p.17¹

Nevertheless, childhood cancer remains the leading cause of death in children after accidents (e.g. in Europe, in Australia, and the USA).¹³ Unfortunately, in low and middle-income countries, access to treatment is very poor, and an unknown proportion of children with potentially curable cancers remain undiagnosed and/or never receive treatment.¹³

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2. SURVIVORSHIP

2.1 LATE CONSEQUENCES FOR SURVIVORS

Surviving childhood cancer comes with significant consequences and burden for the daily life of survivors and their families, either due to the impact of cancer itself or its treatment.¹ Because children have yet to reach significant milestones in their physical, social and psychological development, they are particularly vulnerable for late consequences.^{1,2} During the intensive treatment phase, their development may be interrupted and affected until many years after.³

In terms of physical health, survivors remain at increased risk for second malignancies (secondary cancers)⁴⁻⁶, and high risk for late effects of the treatment, which may lead to chronic illness⁷⁻⁹, such as heart disease, abnormal lung function, hormonal deficiencies, and neurocognitive impairments. Among survivors aged 5-19 years, two-thirds already suffer from at least one chronic health condition; by the age of 40, this prevalence reaches 88%.¹⁰ The cumulative prevalence of *any* chronic health condition was reported to be as high as 95.5%; including 80.5% survivors with a serious, disabling or life-threatening condition.¹⁰

As for socioeconomic consequences, survivors of childhood cancer report altered educational paths¹¹, lower income¹², using more often social benefits¹³, and being unemployed more often¹³ than comparison-groups. Survivors might also experience difficulties in social adjustments, such as being unable to live independently and showing lower social competence.¹⁴

Regarding psychosocial consequences, survivors show different distributions in relationship status: survivors report less often to have a life partner and less often to be married than comparisons.¹⁵ Furthermore, young adult survivors can be concerned about their fertility and altered body image.^{15,16} Physical changes (e.g. due to surgical removal of cancer, cancer-related fatigue), may additionally burden survivors (e.g. social comparison, social isolation, bullying¹⁷) and may lead to body dissatisfaction and feeling a loss of identity¹⁶.

Other psychological consequences for survivors can be wide-ranging and include psychological distress, post-traumatic stress, anxiety and depression.¹⁸⁻²⁰

2.2 FOLLOW-UP CARE & LOSS TO FOLLOW-UP

Why is follow-up care necessary? Because childhood cancer survivors are prone to develop late effects, attendance of follow-up care long into survivorship is essential to monitor the survivors' overall health. Adequate care and support from specialists including disciplines outside of oncology²¹ are vital to promoting the survivors' health and well-being. Furthermore, regular follow-up care is necessary for survivors to detect the sometimes asymptomatic onset of late effects early. Therefore, it is crucial that even many years after cancer, survivors continue to visit follow-up care, so-called long-term follow-up care (LTFU-care).²¹

How is LTFU-care organised? LTFU-care is not standardised (e.g. Switzerland^{22,23}, Australia^{24,25}). For instance, LTFU-care can take place at a children's or adult hospital, at a general practitioner (GP) practice, or a specialised late effects clinic.²⁶ Accordingly, LTFU-care can be provided by the initially treating paediatric oncologist, a medical oncologist, a GP, paediatrician, or nurse-led telephone/questionnaire follow-up.²³ None of the models for the organisation of LTFU-care have been systematically implemented.²⁶

Risk-stratified follow-up care is currently advocated internationally.²⁶ This model proposes that survivors should receive a specialised care plan taking into consideration their medical history (e.g. types of treatment received and already present late effects to adjust the frequency of visits and specialities involved as recommended). Those guidelines for LTFU-care are continuously updated according to most up-to-date research findings.²⁶

Lack of attendance. Studies have demonstrated that the majority of survivors do not attend to LTFU-care.^{23,27,28} More than ten years after their diagnosis, only 17% of survivors with moderate and 32% with severe late effects had regularly received follow-up care.²³ Rates remained low, even after implementing guidelines and efforts to increase education and awareness of late effects.²³

Barriers. LTFU-care can be perceived as burdensome because it may be complex and difficult to obtain, for instance, due to a wide range of specialist that may be required. After the childhood cancer experience, survivors often want to move on to a life where cancer plays not the centre of attention anymore. Previous research strived to identify models of care that work best for survivors, i.e. in terms of whom to involve and around the organisation of appointments.²⁹

 RESEARCH GAP

While previous efforts addressed environmental and cancer-related factors to promote survivors' engagement in LTFU care, many studies show that most survivors still do not attend LTFU care in the long-term. Underlining psychological factors contributing to disengaging in this health behaviour have been understudied, however they could be useful to inform interventions to increase attendance. Therefore, the objective of study 1 was to apply the *Theory of Planned Behavior* regarding survivors' LTFU-care attendance and to examine further psychosocial and cancer-related characteristics that may be associated with LTFU-care attendance (study 1).

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3. PARENTS

Parents are confronted with a number of challenges that come with caring for a child diagnosed with cancer.¹ In order to manage the intensive treatment phase, parents have to adjust their caregiving habits by reorganising family routines and roles.² Simple tasks such as providing regular meals may become a challenge during this time. Parents were seen to redistribute their roles, so that one parent can stay with the child at the hospital and the other works to assure financial income.¹⁻³ Substantial costs are associated with the cancer experience, including out-of-pocket expenses and lower income due to prolonged absence from work and/or reduced work hours.^{2,4}

3.1 PARENTS' ROLE DURING TREATMENT

Parents, as the primary caregiver of the child, play a central role to support the provision of treatment. They have to collaborate with health-care professionals and have to orient themselves within the health-care system to manage their child's complex treatment successfully. At the hospital, the children are confronted with many unfamiliar situations and may further be challenged by homesickness.⁵ Parents are required to manage their child's behaviour (e.g. regarding sleep disturbances, loss or increase of appetite due to medication) and emotional state (e.g. facing pain, or nausea).⁵

Parents are further involved in administering medical care, pain management and monitoring the child's treatment and treatment-related symptoms (i.e. unwanted side effects).^{6,7} The treatment, often is organised in phases, such as recurring cycles of chemotherapy.⁶ The treatment plan is adjusted as needed, depending on the child's response to treatment. Treatments usually last over an extended period of time, several months or years (e.g. for leukaemia usually between one to three years), including several overnight hospital-stays.⁶

Parents are also involved in treatment-related decisions.⁸ For instance, they are responsible for deciding if their child should be enrolled in a clinical trial.⁹ Consequently, they will need to understand what a clinical trial is, and what it specifically means for their individual case. Parents act as advocates for their child, because they know best how their child feels and reacts to certain situations.⁸

The life-threatening nature of cancer and its often long-lasting treatment represents a challenge for the child diagnosed with cancer and its entire family (e.g. parents/caregivers, siblings, grandparents).^{1,10-12} Commonly reported family experiences include the disruption of family life, isolation, and exhaustion.¹³ If the child has (a) sibling(s), child-minding needs to be organised, and the disease explained to the sibling at an appropriate level for their development. The cancer experience and its long-term impact may also extend to, and affect, the broader social environment.^{10,12}

3.2 HEALTH-CARE EXPERIENCES

Communication is key. During the treatment time, health-care professionals have an enormous influence on families, including the influence on parents' own perceptions of competence to manage the illness and their problem-solving strategies to face the challenges posed by each treatment phase.^{1,8} Family members are particularly vulnerable at the time of diagnosis.^{1,8} Therefore, health-care professionals need to be careful and sensitive in their communication, including their explicit interactions and implicit messages conveyed by their behaviour.¹⁴ Initial interactions could determine the quality of the working-relationship between parents and health-care professionals, and ultimately influence the quality of the treatment and health-care experience.^{1,8}

Parents' health-care & communication experiences. The parent who stays at the hospital has to take on a load of information provided by different health-care professionals (e.g. doctors, nurses, exercise physiologists, etc.). Parents have reported being challenged by the considerable amount of cancer-specific information they have to rapidly acquire, and with navigating through the complex health-care system.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ Furthermore, the treatment itself and its associated decisions are often filled with tension. Conflicts may arise due to different views of parents and health-care professionals.¹⁹ For example, disagreements on how much information should be disclosed to the child about the cancer's severity.²⁰ Additionally, fathers have expressed that health-care professionals are often more focused on providing support to mothers, which leaves them feeling less valued and distant from the child's care.²¹ Dissatisfaction and negative interactions with the health-care team have been associated with decreased parental psychological functioning.²²

Parents' long-term engagement. Parents hold crucial information for the child's survivorship, such as their child's medical history. Even when survivors become adults, many parents remain involved in their follow-up care, for both personal (e.g. information on the child's health status) and practical (e.g. transportation) reasons.²³⁻²⁵ A study showed that 90% of parents are still actively involved in the survivors' follow-up care.²⁴ Despite that, to our knowledge, there is still no study investigating parental health-care and communication experiences with health-care professionals during treatment and into survivorship.

RESEARCH GAP

To this day, little is known about parents' experiences in interacting with the health-care team, during and especially after the end of treatment. Moreover, current studies lack consideration of psychological models to explain the interaction.⁵ A closer understanding of underlying psychological mechanisms that underlie parents' challenges could disclose new ways of helping parents and satisfying their (information) needs.^{5,24} Consequently, the aim of study 2 was to examine parents' health-care and communication experience with health-care professionals during, and after the child's curative treatment (study 2).

3.3 POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS

Psychological impact. The diagnosis and treatment phases are a rollercoaster journey with its ups and downs and represent a highly stressful time for most parents. The treatment strategy to counter the cancer is unpleasant, often toxic, and also uncertain.¹⁷ Parents are confronted with a life-threatening disease, and the thought that the condition could be terminal or with permanent life-limiting consequences. Many parents show high levels of distress^{26,27}, anxiety^{26,27}, depression²⁸, and increased levels of post-traumatic stress^{29,30}. Parents often start processing the cancer experience only after the intense and demanding treatment period has ended. A significant proportion of them continues to experience psychological difficulties in the long run.

Trauma. Following a potentially traumatic event, it is a natural psychological reaction to experience so-called post-traumatic stress symptoms (PTSS). In the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, fourth edition (DSM-IV), PTSS are classified into three symptom-groups including *intrusion*, *avoidance*, and *hyperarousal* (Figure 3³¹).³²

Figure 3. Examples of post-traumatic stress symptoms for the symptom-groups intrusion, hyperarousal, and avoidance.

Sources: theadventurer, 2017³¹; APA, 2015³²

PTSD. If PTSS are severe and persist for more than one month after the exposure to the potentially traumatic event, a diagnosis of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) could be diagnosed.³³ Among parents of childhood cancer survivors, it is reported that between 27% to 54% will be assigned such a diagnosis during their lifetime.²⁹

Dynamics. Longitudinal studies have shown that PTSS in parents of children on active cancer treatment are elevated but decrease after treatment ends. Nevertheless, five years post-diagnosis, a non-neglectable subset of parents report clinically relevant levels of PTSS, with 19% of mothers and 8% of fathers presenting partial PTSD. Traumatic events and PTSD have an important influence on the individuals' health and everyday-life.³⁴

RESEARCH GAP

PTSS and prevalence of PTSD have not yet been studied in parents of *very long-term* childhood cancer survivors. Studies investigating the psychosocial health and well-being of parents of childhood cancer survivors, including PTSS and PTSD, have been conducted only within the first six years after diagnosis and using small samples.²⁹ The complications and uncertainties associated with childhood cancer may continue to burden parents mentally, socially and financially. Little is known on parents' stress symptoms in the long run, many years after their child's diagnosis and treatment, when survivors are grown-up. Therefore, in study 3, we describe levels of PTSS, PTSD, and the characteristics associated with PTSS in parents of very long-term survivors (study 3).

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CHAPTER 2 OBJECTIVES

Chapter 2 summarises the specific objectives of this thesis, based on the existing literature, and the thereby identified research gaps.

STUDY 1 – SURVIVOR’S FOLLOW-UP CARE ATTENDANCE

Childhood cancer survivors are at risk for physical and psychosocial late consequences. Only few survivors attend essential follow-up care in the long term. There is a lack of research investigating the psychological characteristics associated with survivors’ behaviour regarding LTFU-care. Therefore, (i) we applied the *Theory of Planned Behavior* – a behaviour change theory that has been widely used to address and explain individuals’ health behaviours. (ii) We further examined psychosocial and cancer-related characteristics associated with LTFU-care attendance in long-term survivors of childhood cancer.

STUDY 2 – PARENTS’ HEALTH-CARE EXPERIENCES

Parents play an essential role both during the child’s treatment and long into survivorship. Little is known about parents’ experiences when interacting with the health-care team during the treatment phase and into survivorship. We (i) investigated the parents’ health-care experience during and after their child’s treatment, and (ii) developed a theory to help explain parents’ experiences in interacting and communicating with health-care professionals.

STUDY 3 – POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS IN PARENTS

Little is known on how parents fare in the long term psychologically. A significant proportion of parents develop PTSD at some point in the childhood cancer trajectory. It is not yet established if PTSS in parents of survivors resolve over time. We compared parents of very long-term childhood cancer survivors to parents of the Swiss general population with adult children. We investigated: (i) the type of self-identified most stressful event, (ii) the reported PTSS and the prevalence of PTSD, and (iii) the characteristics associated with PTSS, and we further provided (iv) norm-data for the Swiss general population.

CHAPTER 3 EPISTEMOLOGY & METHODOLOGY

In Chapter 3, I will briefly outline the epistemological stance, the theories and frameworks embraced in the presented research, and provide an overview of the applied methodologies (quantitative and qualitative methods).¹⁻³

1. EPISTEMIOLOGICAL STANCE

1.1 PRAGMATISM: BRIDGING POST-POSITIVISM & CONSTRUCTIVISM

For the present thesis, a pragmatic paradigm was adopted.¹ This epistemological stance acknowledges the plurality of knowledge, hence accepting the variety of forms of knowledge and perspectives as well as recognising competing interests of stakeholders. Knowledge is seen as a tool to serve a specific purpose, and therefore can be evaluated for its fit to the goals or interests (i.e. aims).⁴ Meanwhile, pragmatists are suspicious of efforts to single out, and privilege, one point of view over another. Accordingly, there is no superior method to another. Instead, it is critical that methods are chosen carefully to match them appropriately with the research's aims. Meanwhile, the critical evaluation of the processes involved in the knowledge generation is considered fundamental; for instance, whose interests are being served.

1.2 POST-POSITIVISM

In a traditional positivist perspective, the researcher can "objectively" observe an "independent reality" which is under study. Within a post-positivist perspective the fallibility of observations is recognised. This perspective is practised today by researchers using quantitative methods such as inferential statistics, which represent a tool that emphasises on probabilities of the findings to be "true". There is an understanding that the findings never completely reflect and explain the "reality", but are an approximation; hence the aim is to find the best possible estimation.⁴ This perspective has dominated in psychological sciences since its establishment.⁴ Some of the disadvantages that come with this posture and its tools are that the data is disconnected from its context that gives meaning.⁵ Using closed questions and standardised scales, often it is not possible to seize the underlying psychological processes at hand, and the meaning and implications for daily living of a situation for individuals.

1.3 CONSTRUCTIVISM

In a constructivist perspective, the researcher's active role in the process, from study design over data collection to analysis of results, is recognised.⁴ The "truth" is not considered to exist in some external world but is understood to be created by the individual's interactions with the world. In this sense, the meaning is *co-constructed* and hence shaped by social, cultural and historical happenings.² Consequently, multiple, contradictory but equally valid accounts of the world may co-exist.⁶ Some of the disadvantages that come with this posture and its tools are that the data is often collected only in a sub-sample of the population under investigation, which often limits generalisation to the overall population. With more in-depth data collection (e.g. semi-structured interviews, memos), the data collection and analysis is also often more time consuming for participants and researchers.

1.4 PRAGMATISM IN HEALTH RESEARCH

For health research, the pragmatist but critical perspective recognises that biomedical knowledge is essential for patients, supporting the prevention of health problems, relieving symptoms or curing illnesses. This knowledge is instrumental in managing health conditions. However, health education has been criticised for taking this information (e.g. resulting from a randomised controlled trial), assuming that laypeople who are provided with this information will think and act rationally. From a pragmatist point of view, this biomedical knowledge is often "*not very useful or actionable in relation to the needs of lay people*" p.13.¹ In the context of chronic illness, individuals draw on medical, non-medical and even anti-medical knowledge to create their health identities.¹ Meanings, strategies and skills, as much as facts, can be valuable for an individual whose life, relationships, work and identity are changing through illness. Even for relatively clearly defined objectives, such as giving up smoking or physical activity (or going to follow-up care as in study 1).

1.5 CONCLUSION

In this thesis, I embrace an epistemological stance that allows for an approach to methodology that is reflexive and flexible, rather than dogmatic.^{7,8} The pragmatic stance acknowledges that the disciplinary understanding and experience are important when applying existing methodologies meaningfully and recognises that "logics-in-use" are rarely pure, but can – and should - be tailored to the research's aim(s).

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2. GUIDING THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Frameworks and theories are vital tools in health promotion practice and research.² They help to develop an organised, systematic and efficient approach to research and health promotion programs and to identify determinants more quickly and effectively.² However, no single framework or theory usually fits all needs since study aims or objectives of interventions are often multifaceted and interdisciplinary. Common to frameworks and theories is the aim to describe a phenomenon including relationships between concepts and to facilitate the identification for points of intervention.

2.1 BEHAVIOUR CHANGE MODELS

Specific to behaviour change models, is that the theoretical constructs include concepts such as barriers and facilitators to change (including beliefs, attitudes, social norms), and the notions of perceptions, self-efficacy, outcome expectations, and support to maintain change (cultural, historical, and environmental context).² For study 1, we chose the *Theory of Planned Behavior* after Ajzen (1991) to describe the follow-up attendance of adult childhood cancer survivors.³ As explained in publication 1, page 2⁴ :

"The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed in 1985 has become one of the most influential models in predicting a diverse range of health behaviors^{3,5}. The intention to perform a specific behavior is understood to result from three underlining constructs: Attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control (perceived control). Attitude is composed of personal evaluations of the negative and positive consequences of the behavior. Subjective norm incorporates the individuals' perceived social pressure to perform the behavior. For instance, their estimation of how close ones would like them to behave. Perceived control reflects whether a person feels able to enact the behavior; it includes the actual control necessary to perform the behavior and, how confident the person feels to perform this behavior. It is expected that a positive attitude, the perception that close friends, family and other important people support the behavior, and the expectation that one has personal control over a behavior will increase the intention to actually perform the behavior. Moreover, with higher intention, people are expected to be more likely to perform the behavior. Because a certain degree of actual control over the behavior is necessary for behavioral performance, perceived control is also understood to have a direct impact on behavioral performance itself." (Figure 4)

Figure 4. The *Theory of Planned Behavior* according to Ajzen (1991) with the example of follow-up attendance as a health behaviour.

Source: Baenziger et al., 2018⁴

2.2 THE EMBODIED-SOCIETAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

A co-constructivist perspective in health psychology guided the conduct and analysis of study 2.⁶ In this perspective, the individuals' lived experience is seen as co-constructed through continuous interactions between the psychological, social and physiological states. The *Embodied-Societal-Psychological Perspective* (ESP) is based on conceptions proposed by Wallon (the primary function of emotions), and Vygotsky (development of superior psychological functions). This approach aims to be reflective, including interplays between morals, emotions, ethics, and politics that underline the experience of health and illness.^{6,7} Recent research on neurophysiological foundations and early interactions go in line with those propositions.⁸⁻¹⁰ The perspective is particularly helpful in explaining the lived experience of individuals that are affected by a crisis of serious illness, and how s*he assigns meaning to it, taking into account its interplays with the society's and/or family's responses to the illness.

2.3 INTEGRATIVE TRAJECTORY MODEL OF PEDIATRIC MEDICAL TRAUMATIC STRESS

Study 3 can be situated within the integrative model of *Paediatric Medical Traumatic Stress* (PMTS, Figure 5). It is a conceptual framework to understand the psychological reactions of severely injured or ill children and their families.¹¹ It is based on a systematic review of the literature conducted in 2006 (Kazak et al.)¹¹ and has been updated in 2016 (Price et al.)¹², to describe the psychological and physiological responses to injury and serious illness including medical procedures (e.g. invasive or frightening) and pain. The model groups the different trajectories an individual may encompass, divided into three phases:

Phase 1 includes the initial potentially traumatic event, in its context, such as the medical communication (e.g. regarding diagnosis and treatment), transportation, hospital environment and urgent procedures.

Phase 2 includes the early, evolving and ongoing responses concerning medical treatment and its demands.

Phase 3 includes long-term responses beyond the potentially traumatic event and its active medical treatment; implying that the trauma response may potentially continue for months and even years.

Figure 5. The *Integrative Trajectory Model of Medical Traumatic Stress*, including the medical phases and the possible psychological responses to paediatric injury and illness. Recommendations for psychosocial assessment and interventions for clinical practise are outlined on the bottom.

Source: Price et al., 2016¹²

Post-traumatic stress symptoms (PTSS) are considered a common and natural immediate reaction to trauma, which can resolve on its own over time. However, the PMTS highlights the potential for trauma to continue long into survivorship (which we investigated for parents of childhood cancer survivors in study 3 aim 2. Prevalence of PTSS and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)).

The model further provides a guide for the assessment and intervention for patients and their parents, based on the growing empirical evidence. In phase 1, the aim is to change the subjective experience of the potentially traumatic event. In phase 2, the aim is to prevent clinically relevant PTSS/PTSD. In phase 3, the aim is to reduce PTSS.

Also, within the more specific context of childhood cancer, a trauma framework that includes PTSS and PTSD, is embraced to better understand the distress related to paediatric cancer.¹³ The model proposed by Bruce (2006) depicted in Figure 6 further guided the identification of determinants for PTSS and PTSD (Study 3 Aim 3, e.g. time and age as explanatory variables, individual and cancer-related characteristics).

Figure 6. Determinants for cancer-related PTSS and PTSD in children and their parents.

Source: Bruce, 2006¹³

2.4 CONCLUSION

Above, I highlighted the principle guiding models for the analysis of each study. However, it is essential to remember that frameworks, models and approaches are not meant to be mutually exclusive but rather complement each other to help explain different aspects of an outcome. This is also valid for the methods applied in this thesis, which are further explained in the following.

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3. METHODS

3.1 QUANTITATIVE

General approach. All statistical analyses were carried out using the software Stata 15 and within the principles of medical statistics.¹ For all studies, we used descriptive and chi-square statistics to describe the study population(s). For the regression models (Study 1, Study 3), we used a stepwise approach to logistic (dichotomous outcome variables) and linear (continuous outcome variables) regression models respectively, to identify characteristics associated with the primary outcome. Only variables that were associated in univariable models were included in multivariable models

For study 1, we further refined our model using a *Structural Equation Modelling* approach, based on the instructions after Acock.² We estimated the goodness-of-fit of the model (how well the sample data is described by the model) with the recommendations provided by Schermelleh-Engel³, and reflections on assumptions by Kline⁴.

For study 3, we proceeded with a *Multilevel Modelling* approach based on Twisk, as well as Goldstein^{5,6} taking to account for the potential similarities within families/households due to our research design. Student t-tests were used to compare the study populations regarding the prevalence of PTSD-cases and levels of PTSS.¹ Furthermore, given the explorative nature of the research question (i.e. aim 3 which is exploring the characteristics associated with PTSS), we decided to adjust for the family-wise error rate (the probability that one or more Type I error (false positives) will occur) by applying the Bonferroni-Holm adjustment.⁷

3.2 QUALITATIVE

General approach. Qualitative data analysis was carried out for study 2 and aim 1 in study 3 with two unique *coding* approaches outlined in more detail below. In general, "*coding*" refers to the act of "*sensemaking*" of the data of interest – it requires the qualitative analysts to read the data in its context and to separate segments which can be "*coded*" to assign a particular meaning to each of them. In this thesis, we started with identifying

subcategories, clustering them into categories with similar meaning, and finally identifying common overarching themes (which are mutually exclusive). This data analysis approach is an iterative process, signifying that the “coding tree” (see Figure 7) is continuously adjusted in terms of recurring subcategories and

Figure 7. Prototype coding tree with subcategories, categories and overarching themes.

Source: Baenziger (unpublished)

Study 2 involved a rigorous approach within qualitative health psychology, applying the principles of *Grounded Theory* after Glaser & Strauss.³⁰ An inductive, hypothesis-generating approach was needed due to the lack of existing literature regarding the topic and the statement that a new theory is needed to help explain the health-care communication experiences of parents of children with cancer. In *Grounded Theory*, it is understood that the researcher has no previous understanding of the phenomenon, or at least should reflect upon the potential preconceptions. The results thus are expected to be “grounded” in the observations or data. *Grounded Theory* is an approach that has its origin in sociology and is critical and co-constructivist. This approach looks at experiences and at as many other data sources as possible to develop a more objective understanding of the subject of the study. The goal is to develop a new theory or model to explain the phenomenon. We used the software *Nvivo 12* to manage and analyse the data, constructing subcategories (called *nodes* in *Nvivo*), categories and themes. We discussed categories and themes regularly in team meetings and reflected on our postures and preconceptions in an iterative process.

Study 3 required the classification of experienced events in terms of content.¹¹ We grouped similar events into categories with an open-coding approach, and in a second step, identified overarching themes with the help of

the *Post-traumatic Stress Disorder Checklist*.¹² We then proceeded to count the number of occurrences (frequency count) among participants reporting such types of events in the respective categories and themes (see Supplementary Digital Content 2, Study 3).¹¹ For this analysis, we used the *Microsoft Office 356* software *Excel*.

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CHAPTER 4 POPULATION & PROCEDURES

In this chapter, I will briefly situate the three studies of the present doctoral thesis in their context, namely regarding their respective larger research project. Study 1 was part of the Childhood Cancer Follow-Up Study (paragraph 4.1.3). Study 2 was part of the randomised-controlled-trial Cascade (paragraph 4.2.4). Study 3 was part of the project Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study – Parents (paragraph 4.1.3 and 4.1.4). I will start by outlining the Swiss context regarding research in childhood cancer (where I am a PhD Candidate at the University of Lucerne), and proceed to contextualise the Cascade study of the Behavioural Sciences Unit at the Children’s Hospital in Sydney (where I was a visiting PhD Candidate during 03/2018-03/2019).

1. SWISS RESEARCH CONTEXT

1.1 THE SWISS CHILDHOOD CANCER REGISTRY

History. The SCCR was founded by the *Swiss Pediatric Oncology Group (SPOG)*, which is the national organisation of all paediatric oncologists and associated professions. The nine SPOG member institutions include the *Kantonsspital Aarau, Universitäts- und Kinderspital beider Basel (UKBB), Universitäts-Kinderspital Zürich, Kinderspital Luzern, Ostschweizer Kinderspital, Inselspital Bern, Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV), Hôpital des Enfants* in Geneva and *Ospedale San Giovanni* in Bellinzona. The extensive database is hosted by the *Institute for Social and Preventive Medicine (ISPM)* at the University of Bern. As of 2020, the *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry* has become the *Childhood Cancer Registry (ChCR)* of the Federal Government, recording all diagnosed children and adolescents under 20 years of age across Switzerland.^{1,2}

Registration & data- In Switzerland, every patient diagnosed before the age of 21 with cancer according to the ICC-3 or Langerhans cell histiocytosis has been centrally registered since 1976. The SCCR is one of the oldest and most complete registries for childhood cancer. It has been shown that the registries’ completeness is likely over 95%.⁶ Detailed clinical data on cancer-related characteristics such as diagnosis, treatment, relapse, and late effects are stored (in the SCCR, Figure 8). To assure confidentiality, contact details, such as names and addresses of childhood cancer patients and their parents, are stored in a separate database - the *Trust Centre*. Personal and identifying data of the registry is only connected to the SCCR by a *Unique Identifier (UID)*.

Figure 8. Overview of the complexity in running a centralized registry for children diagnosed with cancer.

Source: *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry* (unpublished)

Recruitment through the SCCR. To establish contact, for instance, to recruit for ongoing research projects, there is yet another database called *Tracking*. With the use of the UID, contact information can be temporally extracted, e.g. to generate an address in order to facilitate the mailing of questionnaires. Every contact with a registered person or any relatives (e.g. parents or siblings) is tracked in this separate *Tracking* database, using only the UID. This database is especially critical to avoid recruiting persons to studies who refused to be contacted or to avoid inviting individuals to participate in multiple studies at the same time (avoiding excessive burden).

1.2 THE SWISS CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVOR STUDY

The *Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study (SCCSS)* conducted between 2007 – 2011, was the first questionnaire-based survey among all survivors diagnosed before the age of 16 years with cancer according to the ICCC-3⁷ between 1976 and 2003.⁸ Eligible for participation were survivors who were a minimum of 5 years post-diagnosis and who had Swiss residency at the time of diagnosis. The study included psychosocial measures, such as quality of life⁹, health behaviours, somatic health, psychological distress⁷, health-care use, and sociodemographic information.¹⁰

1.3 THE CHILDHOOD CANCER FOLLOW-UP STUDY

Aim. The SCCSS studies have been complemented by a study on follow-up care after childhood and young adult cancer, called the *Childhood Cancer Follow-Up (CCFU)* study, circulating a questionnaire survey between 2009-2014. This project aimed to assess opinions on currently used or desired optimal follow-up care.

Study design. This project included the perspectives of childhood cancer survivors, adolescent and young adult cancer survivors, parents of adolescent survivors and physicians. In the following, I will focus on the sample of childhood cancer survivors.

Eligibility. Concerning survivors of childhood cancer, those who participated in the SCCSS (cf. point 1.2), who were diagnosed between 1990 – 2007, aged 18-25 at time of the study, were invited to participate.

Recruitment & materials. The survey for childhood cancer survivors included questions on follow-up care attendance (e.g. items measuring the constructs needed for the *Theory of Planned Behavior*⁹⁹), survivors' needs for future follow-up care, psychological distress (*Brief Symptom Inventory-18, BSI-18*)¹⁰², brief illness perception questionnaire (*Brief-IPQ*), post-traumatic growth¹⁰³; and on sociodemographic information. An invitation letter was sent to survivors, including study information, questionnaire, informed consent sheets, and a pre-paid return envelope. A reminder was sent after two months.

Ethics approval was granted through the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Bern to the SCCR and SCCSS (KEK-BE: 166/2014).

CCFU population. Of 761 eligible survivors, 687 could be contacted, and 320 responded (46.6%). For **Study 1** of the present thesis¹¹, three had to be excluded because their parents filled out the questionnaire, and 18 did not complete the section regarding the follow-up attendance to measure items in accordance with the *Theory of Planned Behaviour* – the sample thus consisted of 299 survivors (166 females, 55.5%, and 133 males (44.5%)).

1.4 THE CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVOR STUDY – PARENTS

Aim. The *Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivors Study – Parents (Parents-Study)* was the first Swiss nationwide study focusing on late psychosocial outcomes in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors. The overall aim of the project was to assess and evaluate psychological and sociodemographic outcomes, as well as support needs, in parents of long-term survivors of childhood cancer (CCS-Parents).

To have an adequate comparison group, data of a representative sample of the Swiss general population was collected. With this data, an additional aim is to provide Swiss norm-data for established and frequently used instruments, such as quality of life¹², psychological distress (data analysis ongoing), and post-traumatic stress.¹

Ethical approval was granted for the study by the *Ethikkommission Nordwest- and Zentralschweiz* (EKNZ) (reference: EKNZ 2015-075).

PARENTS OF LONG-TERM CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVORS

Eligibility. CCS-Parents were eligible if their child was: diagnosed with cancer at age ≤ 16 years and registered in the SCCR (diagnosed between 1976-2009), a Swiss resident at diagnosis, had survived ≥ 5 years, was ≥ 20 years old at the time of the study, and alive at the time of the study ($n=2714$). Parents' addresses were extracted from the SCCR and verified with online directories. CCS-Parents were contacted when a valid address was available. This resulted in a sample of parents of 1227 eligible survivors.

Randomisation. Parents were randomised on survivor-level into two groups to contact them in two distinctive ways (January 2017 - November 2017): Half of CCS-Parents were contacted blinded, framed as "parents of the general population", thus receiving the exact same questionnaire as individuals of the Swiss general population. The other "unblinded" group of CCS-Parents was contacted as "parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors". They received the same questionnaire, plus additional questions on late psychosocial consequences of the childhood cancer experience.

Recruitment & materials. Parents in the “unblinded” group were first contacted with the study invitation sent by mail coming from the paediatric oncologists of the original treatment clinic. Study invitation for the “blinded” group was mailed from the study centre at the University of Lucerne. Subsequently, all parents received the questionnaire package from the study centre. Two weeks after the study invitation including the study information, we mailed two copies of the questionnaire - one for each parent to fill out individually, and two prepaid return-envelopes. Non-respondents received up to two reminders after approximately 4 and 12 weeks. All study material was available in German, French and Italian, to account for the three main language regions in Switzerland.

Population CCS-Parents. Parents of 1167 survivors could be contacted; 153 parents refused (Table 2). For 511 (43.8%) survivors, at least one parent participated. This resulted in a sample of 784 parents (323 fathers, 461 mothers) for the CCS-Parents.

<i>Parents of survivors</i>	blinded		unblinded		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Total Eligibles	621	100	606	100	1,227	100
Contacted	593	95.48	574	94.72	1167	95.11
Responders	206	33.17	305	50.33	511	41.65
Non-Responders	286	46.05	217	35.81	503	40.99
Refusals	101	16.26	52	8.58	153	12.47
Not Contacted	28	4.51	32	5.29	60	4.88
Wrong address	19	3.06	23	3.8	42	3.42
Unable	4	0.64	5	0.83	9	0.73
Deceased	5	0.81	4	0.66	9	0.73
Response rate	34.74%		53.14%		43.79%	

Table 2. Response rates among parents of childhood cancer survivors according to randomised group (blinded [University] vs unblinded [Clinics]).

Source: Baenziger (unpublished)

Important to note is that due to incompletely filled-out questionnaires, the final n of participants slightly differs in study 3 compared to the overall participation rate in the CCS-Parents (see supplementary digital content SDC Figure 1. of study 3).

THE SWISS GENERAL POPULATION & COMPARISON GROUP

Eligibility. We received a random sample of 3'000 representative households drawn according to the language distribution of the Swiss general population (SGP) from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office. Of 7'052 identified individuals, 5'644 were aged between 18 - 75 years (in 2015) and eligible to participate.

Study design. Eligible individuals were randomised on the household level into two groups to contact them in two distinctive ways (June 2015 - June 2016): Half of the participants were invited as "comparison-group" to our study on health and well-being in parents of childhood cancer survivors. This information was stated in the study invitation letter and on the questionnaire. The other half was contacted without mentioning of the CCS-Parents and asked to participate in a study on health and well-being in the Swiss population.

Recruitment & materials. Every potential participant was invited with an individual invitation letter, including study information. Approximately two weeks later, we sent the questionnaire with a cover letter and prepaid return envelope. Non-responders received a second copy of the questionnaire between four and six weeks after sending the first questionnaire. All study material was available in German, French and Italian.

Population SGP. Of 5'315 contacted individuals, 1'255 (23.6%) participated. The response rate was 21.3% among parents who were informed about the comparison with parents of childhood cancer survivors, and 26.1% among participants who were not informed about the comparison with parents of childhood cancer survivors.

Population comparison-parents. Parents having at least one child aged 20 years or older were identified among the Swiss general population and used as a subsample to compare them with the CSS-Parents. This sample consists of 471 parents, including 199 (42.3%) fathers and 272 (57.8%) mothers.

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2. AUSTRALIAN RESEARCH CONTEXT

2.1. THE BEHAVIOURAL SCIENCES UNIT

The *Behavioural Sciences Unit* (BSU) at the *Kids Cancer Centre of Sydney's Children's Hospital* is the largest research group dedicated to paediatric psycho-oncology throughout Australia and New Zealand.² The BSU is affiliated with the *University of New South Wales* (UNSW).

The Unit is organised in five working groups: *Mental Health, Cognition & Education, Health Behaviour, Ethics & Genetics, and Nutrition*. They conduct cancer research across all trajectories from diagnosis through survivorship and bereavement and from young patients to parents and grandparents. Furthermore, they have worked for over twelve years with these populations³ and aim to improve support for families of childhood cancer patients and survivors.

Figure 9. Overview of ongoing and past studies at the "BSU" in 2018.

Source: Behavioural Sciences Unit (unpublished)

2.2 GUIDING FRAMEWORK

The BSU's research, and in particular the study *Cascade*, are guided by the *Family Systems Illness Model (FIS)*.

The FIS after Rolland (1987, 2004) is evidence-based (data from 800 families) and promotes a systemic family-based therapy approach. The focus lies on illness as experienced through wider family/caregiving systems (e.g. parent, siblings, grandparents) and relational systems (e.g. school, support networks), not just by the child with the diagnosis.

The FIS takes into account the dynamics of the family system including the development of each family member (e.g. individual lifecycle challenges (such as older children reaching adolescence and leaving home), multigenerational patterns of coping with illness/legacies (e.g. ways of thinking about the illness which is handed down from one generation to the next within families), and loss, and their belief systems (e.g. such as views on the cause of the illness; including influences of culture, ethnicity, spirituality, and gender).^{4,5} The emphasis lies on the *appraisal of the situation* for the adjustment (coping response) to the experience (stressor).

FIS recognises the complexity of raising a child with severe illness/disability and its powerful and long-lasting impact on all family members and its associated burden.⁴⁻⁶ Grounded in a strength-oriented perspective, family relationships are viewed as a potential resource, enabling resilience and growth. To successfully adjust to new experiences in every phase, the individual and the family as a whole requires different skillsets along the childhood cancer trajectory:

When a child has cancer, the whole family needs to adjust to the new challenge. Life-domains of adjustment include 1) creating new meaning for the illness, one that preserves a sense of mastery; 2) grieving for the loss of the family's identity before the illness; 3) accepting that the condition could be permanent (health and changes in the family roles); 4) reorganising to the crises for the short-term (e.g. during child hospitalisation); 5) developing family flexibility in the face of uncertainty and threatened loss; 6) to learn to live with symptoms and their treatment/management, and 7) forming a working-relationship with professionals and the health system.

A variety of family concerns can be identified, understood and addressed such as communication issues, maintaining relationships in the face of caregiving demand, or dealing with the threatened loss.

2.3 THE CASCADE STUDY

Aim. The mental health team within the BSU developed an e-mental health intervention aiming to improve the well-being and quality of life of parents of children who survived cancer.⁷ The intervention called CASCADE (Cope Adapt Survive: Life after CAncEr) targets to support parents' coping with the intensive and demanding cancer experience.

Eligibility. Parents were eligible to participate if their child (aged <16 years) had completed cancer treatment with curative intent at the time of recruitment (population-based).⁸ Parents were not eligible if they had insufficient English proficiency or if they reported extremely severe distress (e.g. current suicidal risk at assessment).

Study design. *Cascade* is designed as a randomised controlled trial (Figure 10). Parents are randomly allocated to one of three settings: the intervention (cognitive behavioural therapy, also known as CBT), the active control (peer support) or the waitlist control.^{7,8} The intervention includes four weekly 90-minute sessions facilitated by a psychologist, applying directive structured teaching of specific cognitive-behavioural coping skills.

The active control consists of a peer support group where parents are encouraged to exchange information and to give each other emotional and practical support. The waitlist control group is only interviewed at the entry into the study and receives no intervention for the initial six weeks, after which they have the possibility to participate in one of the interventions.⁷

To guarantee easy access⁹ the sessions are offered in the form of videoconferencing. Groups of three to five parents were facilitated by a psychologist.

Recruitment & materials. *Cascade* is a multicentre study. Parents were recruited through ten Australian hospitals (March 2014 – November 2018). the *Sydney Children's Hospital Randwick*, *The Children's Hospital Westmead*, *Monash Children's Hospital*, *Royal Children's Hospital Melbourne*, *Women's and Children's Hospital Adelaide*, *Royal Adelaide Hospital*, *Royal Children's Hospital Brisbane*, *John Hunter Children's Hospital* and *Princess Margaret Hospital*.

Figure 10. Complex study design of the Cascade survivorship intervention study -

Source: Wakefield et al., 2015^{1,2}

A personalised study invitation letter along with consent form and an opt-out card was sent to eligible study participants. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Parents completed a baseline, semi-structured interview and the *Psychosocial Adjustment to Illness Scale* (PAIS)¹⁰ via telephone. Subsequent video-conferencing sessions were recorded. To collect sociodemographic and cancer-related data (both self-reported), questionnaires were administered online (or paper-based if desired) through *Key Survey* (WorldAPP, Braintree, MA, USA).

Ethics. Lead site ethics approval was obtained from the *Sydney Children's Hospital Network* Human Research Ethics Committee (HNEHREC Reference No: 14/02/19/4.01, NSW HREC Reference No: HREC/14/HNE/44), and all other recruiting sites.

Population Cascade. 76 parents consented to participate. The opt-in rate was available for the *Sydney Children's Hospital* (~25% off all approached parents for the entire Cascade study). The collaborating sites were not able to share any data on parents at their site who did not opt into the study (ethics).

Population PAIS. For the study concerning the section on parents' *Health-care Orientation* using the PAIS, 58 parents could be included (further details see recruitment flowchart in publication 2, Figure 1.¹¹).

2.4 THE AUSTRALIAN CHILDHOOD CANCER REGISTRY

In Australia, public and private hospitals, as well as pathology services, have to report invasive pediatric cancers to the *Australian Paediatric Cancer Registry* (APCR). The APCR is considered to have complete population coverage and to be representative for the Australian population aged 0–14 years as the notification is required by law.¹² In light of data protection laws, the registry is only able to provide summary statistics of a subsample of interest, which prevents data analysis regarding associations between cancer-related, sociodemographic and psychosocial characteristics. Therefore, information on diagnosis and treatment were assessed through self-report of parents participating in *Cascade*.

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CHAPTER 5 RESULTS

STUDY 1 - CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVORS' FOLLOW-UP CARE

Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Christen S, Tinner EM, Kuehni CE, Gummy-Pause F, & Michel G.

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain attendance to follow-up care of childhood cancer survivors? *Psycho-Oncology*. 2018; **27**(6), 1501-1508. [doi: 10.1002/pon.4680](https://doi.org/10.1002/pon.4680)

Date of publication: 22.02.2018

1.1 PUBLICATION *page 43*

1.2 SUPPLEMENTARY DIGITAL CONTENT *pages 51*

STUDY 2 - PARENTS' HEALTH CARE AND COMMUNICATION EXPERIENCE

Baenziger J, Hetherington K, Wakefield CE, McGill BC, Carlson L, Cohn RJ, Michel G, & Sansom-Daly U.

Understanding parents' communication experiences in childhood cancer: A qualitative exploration and model for future research. *Supportive Care in Cancer*. 2020; **28**, 4467-4476. [doi:10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6)

Date of publication: 11.01.2020

2.1 PUBLICATION *page 56*

STUDY 3 - POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS IN PARENTS

Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Harju E, Ansari M, Waespe N, Scheineman K, & Michel G.

Post-traumatic stress in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors and parents of the Swiss general population. *Journal of Psychosocial Oncology: Research and Practice*. 2020; **2**(3), e024. [doi: 10.1097/OR9.000000000000024](https://doi.org/10.1097/OR9.000000000000024)

Date of publication: 28.07.2020.

3.1 PUBLICATION *page 66*

3.2 SUPPLEMENTARY DIGITAL CONTENT *page 75*

CHAPTER 6 DISCUSSION

This chapter provides 1) a brief overview of findings, 2) adds reflections on the relationships in-between the three studies' findings and resulting future directions in research and practice, 3) continues with discussion of overall strengths and limitations, 4) concludes with applicability for other contexts, and 5) overall conclusion.

1. OVERVIEW OF MAIN FINDINGS

Study 1

Can the theory of planned behaviour help explain follow-up attendance of childhood cancer survivors?

Aims

- 1i) Use the *Theory of Planned Behavior* (TPB) to explain long-term follow-up care (LTFU-care) attendance of childhood cancer survivors
- 1ii) Identify characteristics associated with LTFU-care attendance

Results

- 1i) Using a *Structural Equation Model* approach, the data of childhood cancer survivors showed good model fit to the TPB. The TPB has proven useful to help explain the follow-up attendance of childhood cancer survivors.
- 1ii) Social norms, namely the social pressure and support, were strongly associated with survivors' intention to attend LTFU-care. Perceived control and the intention to attend LTFU-care was positively associated with attendance.

From study 1, we learned that foremost, social norms – such as the perception that the survivors' parents want them to attend LTFU-care – may play a major role in promoting survivors' LTFU-care attendance.

Study 2

Understanding parents' communication experiences in childhood cancer: A qualitative exploration and model for future research.

Aims

- 2i) Examine parents experiences with health-care professionals (HCP) during and after their child's cancer treatment
- 2ii) Develop a model to help explain the parent-HCP communication experience

Results

- 2i) Parents' recounted positive attitudes towards care and positive interactions with HCPs. For example, the perception of high expertise among HCPs and HCPs being responsive to their needs. At the same time, parents also reported a few negative attitudes and interactions, such as the uncertainties associated with the invasive treatment, a perceived lack of communication, and feeling support ended prematurely after their child's active cancer treatment completion.
- 2ii) Parents' attitudes and interactions with HCPs were the basis for building trust in the parent-HCP working relationship. Depending on their degree of trust, parents followed recommendations more closely (high-trust), or focused on being advocates for their child (low-trust). Parents minimised the impact of negative HCP-interactions through internal, rationalising processes.

From study 2, we learned that parents' experiences were predominately positive. However, also half of the parents report negative experiences. Parents' degree of trust in health-care professionals affected the way they engaged in their child's health-care. Our findings demonstrate parents' flexibility in acting as a dynamic buffer between HCP-interactions and their child.

Study 3

Post-traumatic stress in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors compared to parents of the Swiss general population

Aims

- 3i) Describe the types of reported stressful events
- 3ii) Report the prevalence of PTSS and PTSD
- 3iii) Identify characteristics associated with PTSS
- 3iv) Provide normative data for the Swiss general population

Results

- 3i) Among parents of childhood cancer survivors (CCS-Parents), 31.5% reported a childhood-cancer related event, followed by other illness-related events (17.8%) and bereavement (14.8%). In comparison-parents, 27.6% reported an illness-related event and 25.6% bereavement. Other highly stressful events were related to work or education, relationships, accidents, and a few other or unknown events.
- 3ii) No differences were found for the prevalence of PTSS and PTSD between CSS-Parents and comparison-parents. Among CCS-Parents 4.8% and among comparison-parents 6.7% were identified as probable cases with PTSD.
- 3iii) Parents of children with chronic illness reported higher intrusion. Lower education was associated with higher intrusion, avoidance and hyperarousal. No cancer-related characteristics were associated with PTSS in CCS-Parents.
- 3iv) We weighted PTSS and PTSD, weighted according to the representative distribution of gender, age, and language region in the Swiss General Population, showed a prevalence of 5.5% PTSD cases.

From study 3, we learned that CSS-Parents do not seem to be at higher risk for PTSS or PTSD as parents of similar-aged children in the Swiss general population. Nevertheless, we identified that parents of children who suffer from a chronic health condition are at higher risk for elevated PTSS, as well as individuals with lower education.

2. REFLECTIONS

2.1 PARENTS' & HEALTH-CARE PROFESSIONALS' ROLE IN LTFU-CARE

« L'année qui a suivi la fin du traitement de notre fille, elle s'est sentie abandonnée. Pourquoi n'y a-t-il un suivi médical, annuel, afin de sécuriser l'enfant malade. Ce sentiment d'abandon a été difficile à gérer »

Father of 24-year old survivor (female, 10 years at diagnosis)

Within the framework of the *Theory of Planned Behavior* in study 1, we identified subjective social norm to be the major contributor regarding survivors' intention to attend LTFU-care.^{1,2} Since high intention translates into increased attendance^{1,2}, the survivors' surrounding play an essential role in creating the social pressure for them to attend LTFU-care. Two key drivers that shape the perceived social norms of survivors can be identified based on study 1 and 2, as well as the broader literature: parents and health-care professionals.^{1,3}

Parents' involvement. Parents of childhood cancer survivors may be especially suitable to create the necessary social pressure to promote survivors' LTFU attendance due to their close family relationship. They have lived through every step of the treatment with their children, and we know that even if their child, the survivor, is already an adult, they remain engaged in their child's care long into survivorship, for instance, to accompany them to medical appointments.⁴⁻⁶ Hence, parents seem to play a supportive role in survivors' LTFU-care.

For survivors, parents are often the primary source to obtain information regarding their cancer trajectory. When this information is not passed on from parent to child during adolescence and into adulthood, the survivor remains without knowledge regarding past cancer and treatment history, which can be detrimental to the intention and attendance to LTFU-care. In a recent mixed-methods study in the UK, it was found that survivors had a poor understanding of their treatment history and/or the potential for late effects.⁷ Barriers to attending LTFU-care included a lack of information.⁸ However, parents are only able to pass on information to the survivor about LTFU-care if they actually have the respective knowledge.

In study 2 of the present thesis, many parents reported feeling "abandoned" by the health-care system already shortly after treatment ended (on average two years), and struggled to identify where their children can obtain relevant and holistic follow-up care.³ This reflects earlier studies on information needs among parents of

survivors.^{8,9} Without parents' understanding of how to engage in LTFU and to obtain necessary care, we cannot expect them to pass on this knowledge to survivors. Parents have previously reported a need for additional information, especially in regards to managing late effects, and stated lacking information about the future.⁹ With more time after diagnosis and the decrease of health-care visits during follow-up, this lack of information might further increase.¹⁰ Continuous parent and patient education are, therefore, vital.¹¹ Most frequently stated among mothers reason for accompanying survivors to LTFU included concern for their child's health and well-being and desire to know current medical advice, health-care status, reassurance, followed by practical support such as taking the opportunity to ask the doctor questions, and to gather or provide information (e.g. on medical history).¹¹

Health-care professionals' communication. Parents' and survivors' early experiences with the health-care system are important. Parents may act as role models to survivors during treatment and in the early survivorship period. We have shown in study 2 that parents' interactions with health-care professionals shaped the way they engaged in their child's health-care.³ Positive interactions with health-care professionals mitigated the negative attitudes towards treatment, and with increased trust in health-care professionals, parents were able to manage difficult situations more easily.³ Parents' narrative surrounding treatment and care might influence children's attitudes towards the health-care system, such as the belief to benefit and being able to adhere to recommended LTFU-care.

The recent mixed-methods study from the UK also identified that some survivors actually attended LTFU-care *for* health-care professionals; namely, they felt that they owed it to the great care received by health-care professionals and attended LTFU-care to express their appreciation.⁷ Correspondingly, lack of personal interrelationship was named as a barrier to LTFU attendance. It appears like health-care professionals are able to generate a form of "social norm" surrounding the LTFU attendance.

Conclusion. Health-care professionals' communication skills are key to survivors' and parents' understanding of LTFU-care. Parents and their interactions with health-care professionals may impact their children's engagement with the health-care system. Therefore, both parents and health-care professionals play a crucial role in the promotion of the child's follow-up attendance long into survivorship.

IMPLICATIONS

Changing social norms. Researchers and practitioners around the world are currently working on the implementation of a so-called “survivorship passport for care”.^{12,13} Such a survivorship passport contains the necessary information on the survivors’ cancer history, associated medical treatments, and recommendations for LTFU-care.¹³ A survivorship passport is a promising tool to help increase survivors’ attendance to LTFU-care because: 1) It provides parents with the necessary guidance in how to engage in LTFU-care of their child until they are old enough to manage their LTFU themselves, and represents a written record of recommendations that can easily be passed on from parents to adult survivors. 2) It supports health-care professionals in summarising treatment and individualise recommendations¹⁴, and supports them in providing LTFU-care, which might be especially helpful for models of LTFU-care that include general practitioners or nurse-led models. 3) It represents a tool to create an additional form of “social norm”, demonstrating to survivors the necessary and “normal” steps to take after cancer treatment. Survivorship passports might be particularly helpful because they are independent of the model of care the survivor chooses. So far, both health-care professionals and survivors have valued such a passport.^{14,15}

Digitalisation. Provision of adequate information at key time points of the survivorship period can be challenging due to its longevity. Digitalisation of materials and a portal where survivors can view and enter new data could have the potential to improve communication surrounding the survivors’ long-term survivorship. Ideally, online portals that survivors could manage themselves, could be programmed with algorithms that identify survivors who needed an update of their information based on the newest best practice recommendations of LTFU and based on their personal cancer history (data stored in registries). Digitalisation could also signify easier tailoring to the survivors’ preferences, ensuring provided information is meaningful to the individual.⁷ A need for an online platform (ideally organised nationally) to manage LTFU and to improve patient education was also formulated by health-care professionals in Australia and New Zealand.¹⁶ In Switzerland, the association *Childhood Cancer Switzerland* has set-up a competence centre for survivorship issues that offers to survivors and health-care professionals support and information about LTFU, including an online platform (called *suivinet*) for survivors where they can revisit important cancer information^{17,18}, which might foster ongoing surveillance and management.^{7,15} A recent Canadian study showed that the majority of

survivors, parents and health-care professionals preferred an electronic- or web-based format of the survivorship care plan over hard-copy.¹⁵

FUTURE RESEARCH & CHALLENGES

Harmonisation. Challenges for the survivorship passport and clinics include the simultaneously evolving care plans in different countries.^{12,16} This signifies a duplication of resource development between clinics (survivorship care plan templates, clinic systems)¹⁶, which in turn signifies inefficient use of resources which are already scarce. Since 2010, the *International Late Effects of Childhood Cancer Guideline Harmonization Group* (IGHG) represent a worldwide collaborative effort to harmonize guidelines for other recommendations regarding surveillance and late effects after treatment for childhood cancer in order to improve the quality of life for survivors.¹⁹ The IGHG provides a framework for the harmonisation of guidelines.¹⁹ While a survivorship passport should be adaptable to restrictions of the health-care systems in every country, its remains important to harmonise the patient-tailored LTFU recommendations, aligning them with the efforts of harmonising the evidence-based recommendations.¹⁹ An ongoing EU-funded project called *PanCareFollowUp* is currently working on the *European Survivorship Passport* and aims to bring evidence-based, person-centred care to clinical practice.²⁰

Implementation science. To what extend a survivorship passport will help in increasing survivors' knowledge about LTFU and encouraging them to attend will need to be shown. To determine its effectiveness, systematic evaluation is needed. Primary outcomes would include the system-wide increase in the proportion of survivors who have a survivorship passport that complies with the evidence-based clinical recommendations and/or the proportion of health-care professionals providing care according to the recommendations to survivors who use the survivorship passport. Secondary outcomes would include the level of parents and survivors' (once self-managing their care) knowledge and confidence in LTFU-care attendance, and psychosocial outcomes of parents and survivors, such as health-related quality of life (HRQOL).

A North American study showed that among childhood cancer survivors who are at high risk for secondary neoplasms or cardiac dysfunction, only 27% of survivors, and 20% of primary care providers had individualised survivorship care plans.²¹ At the same time, it was shown that those who had a plan were more likely to adhere

to the recommended screening guidelines.²¹ Additional research that accompanies multidisciplinary LTFU-care projects, such as for the LTFU clinic in Liestal that measures survivors' HRQOL, asks about patients' wishes and motivations, before and three months after clinic visits³³, are essential to measuring the progress and effect of interventions.

Digitalisation. There are important hurdles in the digitalisation process that need to be addressed when sharing and storing more and more health-related data through online platforms. Challenges for example include ensuring data protection through the security of information technology systems, and addressing personal fears among patients of leaking data, for instance, to share with their health insurances.

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2.2 TRUST & HEALTH LITERACY IN LTFU-CARE

« We tried to foster a good working relationship between my son and the hospital, and between the siblings and the hospital, because I feel like my son will always be part of the hospital family. So if we can foster a really good relationship, then that will be beneficial for him in the long run, and in the short term too. »

Mother of 10-year old survivor (male, 9 years at diagnosis)

Using an exploratory approach in study 2, we found that parents with high trust in health-care professionals followed recommendations regarding care more closely than those with lower trust.¹ Additionally, high levels of trust helped satiate their information needs and lay their worries in face of uncertainties aside. A trusting HCP-parent relationship further fostered the understanding that survivorship care is a necessity.¹

Trust & active participation in health-care. Trust in health-care professionals has been associated with better mental and physical health outcomes, and more appropriate use of health-care services (e.g. higher adherence, lower emergency visits).³ Other studies have highlighted that trust is fundamental for a working partnership between patients (or their caregivers) and health-care professionals.^{4,5} For instance, in order to absorb information about their disease, patients had to have trust in the working partnership with health-care professionals.⁶ This is especially important in a changing landscape from where the patient is no longer considered as passive recipient of care, but a patient that is allowed and expected to interact and partake in their own health-care, for instance in the form of shared treatment decision-making. This may require patients to understand and evaluate information they receive regarding their diagnosis and treatment.

Health literacy. It is important to note that in our study regarding the health-care and communication experience (study 2), Australian parents were particularly well-educated and seemed to have a very good understanding of health-related information.¹ Some parents even highlighted, that they worked in the health-sector. Those parents hypothesised that the childhood cancer experience would be more difficult to manage for parents unfamiliar with the health-system.

Indeed, health literacy has been associated with higher trust in health-care professionals, the health-care system, and with better health outcomes (Figure 11).⁷⁻⁹ Health literacy can affect people's ability to obtain health-care efficiently, such as understanding the medical instructions, navigating the health-care system, or

seeking additional support from health-care professionals.^{10,11} Insufficient health literacy may further impair communication between health-care professionals and patients.¹²

Figure 11. Integrated model of health literacy:

Interplays of health literacy with (for example) participation, health behaviour, and health services use.

Source: Sorensen, 2012.²

Educational attainment. Health literacy has been brought forward as a potential mechanism to explain the well-established associations between education and health outcomes, and education and health behaviors.^{10,11,13,14} In both, Switzerland and Australia, levels of health literacy are strikingly low, despite their high levels of education on a population level. For Switzerland, it was reported that 51% of residents have problematic or inadequate health literacy.¹⁵ For Australia, it is estimated that 60 % of people have inadequate levels of health literacy.⁷

In study 3, we found that lower education was a risk factor for reporting higher post-traumatic stress symptoms among parents and the Swiss general population as a whole. Parental lower education has also been associated with lower HRQOL in Swiss survivors.¹⁶ It is possible that parents with lower education who participated in our *Parents-Study* also had lower health literacy than those with higher education.

Health literacy, illness perceptions & PTSS. Low health literacy and lower education have been associated with more threatening illness perceptions, and lower adherence to treatment.^{17,18} Parents' illness perception might differ from the survivors' and the objective health state.¹⁹ Two studies have shown that mothers of survivors have more negative illness perceptions than survivors themselves.^{19,20} Also a small study showed an

association between mothers' emotional representation of their child's illness and mothers' post-traumatic stress symptoms.²¹ In contrast, constructive or positive health-related beliefs about their child's cancer have been associated with lower psychological distress and higher quality of life in parents accompanying young survivors to follow-up.²²

Health literacy & health beliefs. It has been argued that health literacy could potentially lead to more accurate health beliefs, and medication knowledge.^{23,24} Health beliefs seem to be an important component to address in survivors themselves. For example, Swiss survivors' health beliefs influenced the way they engaged in LTFU-care: While survivors believed LTFU to be effective in detecting and preventing late effects (92%), a large proportion of survivors (80%) rated their susceptibility to late effects low. The belief that LTFU-care was unnecessary was associated with non-attendance.²⁵ Similarly, a majority of Australian survivors believed that they were not at risk for subsequent neoplasms (61.3%) or for developing late effects (48.6%), and those with low levels of risk perception were less likely to attend LTFU-care²⁶ – which is also similar to the findings in the *American Childhood Cancer Survivors Study*.²⁷

Low health literacy is problematic for the health-care system. Low levels of health literacy have been identified as risk factor for poor health, and have been associated with lower adherence, poor use of health services, and higher health-care costs.^{7,28} As such, it can even put an unnecessary strain on the health-care system, because people might mismanage their medication or not adhere to treatment recommendations as they do not understand its necessity. They might even need emergency care or require longer hospitalisations due to delayed support-seeking.⁷ A Swiss study identified that health literacy was significantly associated with either under- and overutilization of health-care.²⁹

Conclusion. Lower health literacy in parents may lead to inadequate illness perceptions regarding their child's health-status and may represent a source of stress. Low health literacy may also prevent parents from finding appropriate support, thus leading to unresolved PTSS in the long-term. Promoting health literacy could facilitate parents' engagement in health-care, helping them to navigate the health-care system regarding necessary LTFU-care, and to obtain psychological support for their own mental well-being.

Additionally, better health literacy could improve survivors' risk perception regarding late consequences, ultimately promoting LTFU-attendance. Health literacy and health beliefs are important concepts to examine

further, because they have the potential to improve interactions with health-care professionals, preventing misunderstandings, and thus negative health-care experiences.

IMPLICATIONS

A public health perspective. Given the high proportions of inadequate and problematic health literacy in the general population (e.g. in the US, among European countries, Switzerland, and Australia), a systematic population-wide promotion of health-literacy seems necessary.^{7,12,14,30} It has also been shown that lower education and having a chronic illness was a risk factor for lower health literacy.^{12,30} Better health literacy may provide important foundation for individuals to engage in conversations regarding their health-care, and become proactive in obtaining adequate health-care. Promoting adequate levels of health literacy in communities has further the potential to reduce health inequalities³¹, and might enable a systemwide increase in delivering more cost-effective high quality care. Ideally, health-literacy should be promoted on a population-level and if possible, starting from childhood, for instance by incorporating health-care education into the school curriculum.

Digital patient files may represent an important milestone towards empowering patient-practitioner communication and facilitating the management of increasing health-care demands. In Australia, such a platform – called *My Health Record* (myhealthrecord.gov.au) – has been implemented nationwide and with an opt-out approach.³² This platform enables patients to track their records of health-care visits and related documents. They can control who has access to documents, remove documents completely, or even nominate a representative to manage the platform. There is also an option for emergency access that allows sharing of data in case of a medical emergency that involves a serious threat to health, life or safety.³²

A similar platform including an *Electronic Patient Dossier* (patientendossier.ch) – (EPD) - is envisioned on the *Strategie eHealth Schweiz 2.0* in Switzerland.³³ The platform is aiming to facilitate information exchange between health-care professionals and institutions.³³ The EPD is voluntary for Swiss citizens and voluntary also for general practitioners, pharmacies, and other services such as Spitex (nursing and caring at home). The EPD participation is only mandatory among hospital and nursing homes.³⁴

Using these platforms, patients are expected to be more engaged in their health behaviours and problems, thus promoting their health literacy.³³

Facilitating care with e-health. Studies have shown that the online interventions enabled disconnected groups to receive support in managing their long-term condition and illness experience; and further empowered them in their interactions with health-care professionals³⁵. Web-based tools have demonstrated effectiveness in increasing (mental) health-literacy³⁶, and could support individuals with low-health literacy in accessing health-care.³⁷ Interventions were more successful if they delivered evidence-based content, had a structured program, were tailored to the target population, and used interactive and experiential learning.³⁶

E-health in the context of childhood cancer. There has been a call to identify optimal ways to communicate to childhood cancer survivors their personal risks without creating unnecessary anxiety²⁶, increasing health literacy in general, may serve this aim. A Canadian study further showed that an online version of the survivorship passport empowered survivors to self-manage their health-care.³⁸ Survivors viewed it as a valuable tool to foster communication with health-care professionals, especially regarding additional psychosocial support.³⁸ Online softwares are also being developed to enhance paediatric patients' engagement in their health-care, fostering timely communication with patients, parents, and health-care professionals to enhance their health-care communication experience.³⁹

An example of e-health to improve parents' of childhood cancer survivors experiences is the web-based treatment decision-aid *Delta*, which fostered parents' understanding of clinical trials.⁴⁰ The online tool supports parents' decision whether to enrol their child in a randomized controlled trial. Using eye-tracking technologies, the webpage content could be adjusted based on parents' visual path.⁴¹

FUTURE STUDIES & CHALLENGES

Health literacy in the context of childhood cancer is in its infancy: A recently published systematic review showed that few studies investigated socio-demographic characteristics that could be associated with health literacy, only *pilot* intervention studies could be identified, and none of the studies investigated the association of health literacy with health outcomes.⁴² It will be critical to evaluate health literacy in future studies, especially as treatment for childhood cancer become increasingly complex.⁴² Patients and parents are expected to understand health-related information that is provided, for instance, to decide whether to enrol their child in a clinical trial.^{40,41} Future research could include measures of health literacy and perception of the survivors'

health status, to better inform interventions that aim at increasing survivors' attendance, and at promoting parental well-being.⁴³

Illness perception. Parents' perception can influence the way they feel and behave towards their child's health and well-being or towards medical care, such as LTFU. For instance, with higher perceived severity of their child's cancer, parents were less likely to seek and understand medical information, and less likely to engage in coping behaviours such as stress management, affective regulation and social support seeking.⁴⁴ In our Swiss *Parents-Study* we unfortunately could not measure parents' illness perception.⁴⁵ It will be interesting to investigate whether this measure might help explain parental psychological outcomes, such as PTSS and post-traumatic growth in the future.

Further research is needed to understand the interplays between illness perception, coping, adherence to treatment, and health outcomes to further inform the development of interventions. Leventhal's Common-sense model of illness could be used to guide further research applying those concepts.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸

Public attitudes regarding e-health. While studies have shown that e-health is overall feasible, acceptable and effective in the Australian context, a German study showed that the general population had a rather negative or ambivalent view regarding e-mental health interventions.⁴⁹ Australians might be more open, and used to, accessing help from remote areas and using technologies to get support (e.g. in form of telephone, videoconference).

A systematic review of Australian e-mental health intervention has shown that barriers to uptake included: lower health literacy, lack of trust, lack of knowledge about e-mental health, low education, and the perception that online programs would not be effective. In contrast, facilitators to participation were higher health-literacy, higher education, anonymity and travel time saved.⁵⁰ Also interesting to note is that men participated, who would otherwise have chosen no help.⁵⁰ Further population-based studies are needed to assess health literacy as well as awareness and attitudes regarding e-health services.

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2.3 PARENTS' STRESS RESPONSE TO ILLNESS & CAREGIVING ROLES

«Was ich ändern würde ist, dass ich für mich psychologische Hilfe suchen würde. Vom Spital hatten wir einmal eine Sitzung, da ich total überfordert war. Weitere Sitzungen wurden vom Ehemann und Sohn abgelehnt. So blieb es bei dieser einen Sitzung. Heute würde ich für mich selber entscheiden und mir Hilfe für mich persönlich holen. Die Müdigkeit unseres Sohnes beschäftigt mich nach wie vor. »

Mother of 41-year old survivor (male, 5 years at diagnosis)

In study 3, we did not find parents of adult survivors to be at an increased risk for post-traumatic stress compared to parents of adult children in the Swiss general population.¹ However, we found out that having a child with a chronic health condition, regardless of the child's age, was associated with reporting higher PTSS.¹ This concerns half of the parents of adult survivors of childhood cancer, and one in four parents of the Swiss general population.¹

Caregiving strains persist for parents of children with chronic illness. Parents may report increased intrusion and hyperarousal due to ongoing caregiving burden. Children who had cancer are particularly vulnerable to chronic health conditions, and consequently so are their parents regarding an ongoing psychosocial burden. Survivors may require continued assistance due to disabilities in consequence of the cancer such as neurocognitive impairments or difficulties in completing every-day chores.^{2,3} These parents may further be challenged on how to disclose the risk for treatment-related late effects to their child as survivors grow older (a topic also highlighted in reflection 1), for example regarding infertility, which could cause anxiety or distress. Late effects and the ongoing dependency of the child on its parents – namely, survivors being financially dependent, living at home, or needing support to carry out daily tasks – was identified by our research group as the main determinant for perceived disadvantages and current support needs in parents of adult survivors.⁴

A Swiss study showed that the functional status of the child, specifically in regards to physical activities and daily living, predicted parental PTSS.⁵ Previous research further showed that parents of children with chronic illness report more burnout symptoms than parents of healthy children.⁶ Also among parents of children with other illnesses, health-related parenting demands may persist long into adulthood, for instance for children with congenital heart disease, children with cognitive impairments, or cerebral palsy.^{7,8}

Parental roles. In earlier studies mothers of childhood cancer survivors were often found to report more psychological distress than fathers.⁹ Also in studies of the adult general population, women were often seen to report more post-traumatic stress symptoms.¹⁰ We did not find any gender differences for PTSS in parents of survivors nor the Swiss general population, after adjusting for the number of children and other socio-demographic variables.¹ Likewise, a meta-analysis showed only minimal gender differences in parenting stress among families with a child with chronic physical illness.⁷

In Switzerland and Australia traditional caregiving roles are still fairly common.^{11,12} This is especially true among parents of childhood survivors: Swiss parents were seen to take on more traditional parenting roles after the diagnosis to manage the illness of their child.¹³ This is also underlined by other studies conducted in Western countries, reporting mothers to spend most of their time with the child (at the hospital) and fathers indicating working more to provide money for household and medical expenses.¹⁴⁻¹⁸ This goes in line with a Swiss study among parents of long-term survivors showing only 9% of mothers but 93% of fathers to be full-time employed.¹⁹ Findings from our *Parents-Study* also show that parents of adult survivors reported similar *security* but higher *dependency* in their partnership than comparisons²⁰ suggesting increased sharing of responsibilities and duties.

“**Gender differences**” have been reported apropos preferred strategies to cope with the challenges faced by cancer: Mothers reported to engage more in emotion-focused strategies such as social support seeking and information seeking and fathers more in problem-focused strategies such as instrumental support and time management.^{14,18} Those differing strategies might, however, represent a reflection of the tasks at hand to solve rather than actual differences in gender. Caring for a sick child poses different challenges, and hence would demand for different strategies to face them, than for instance assuring the financial income of the family. The former is per definition calling for emotion-focussed strategies, for example when trying to help children manage painful treatments, and the later requires more problem-focussed strategies, for example by increasing numbers of work hours and displaying good time-management.

It is interesting to note that for parents who continued to accompany adult survivors into the LTFU-clinics, caregiving burden remained the same whereas objective and family burden decreased compared to parents of children on active treatment.²¹ Financial costs, required time off work, and “little time to spend with family” improved for the parents of adult survivors as compared to parents of children on active treatment.²¹ This study

suggests that possibility, shared duties and roles are not changing in the same way after treatment ended. The burden may decrease more for the “breadwinner” (i.e. financial costs, and work) than the “caregiver” after end of treatment. Continued needs for care of the child after treatment end or with chronic illness may signify an ongoing caregiver burden, resulting in the elevated symptoms among mothers as compared to fathers, given their distribution of roles. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that more caregiving strains were reported by single parents caring for a child with cancer and for children with chronic illness in general.^{22,23}

Psychosocial support & interventions. Findings from our *Parents-Study* further show that many parents reported a need for more support during (67%) and after (34%) active treatment of their child's cancer, and some parents experience support needs long into survivorship.⁴ On average 24 years after the diagnosis, 7% of parents reported support needs today.⁴ While the need for medical, job-related, financial, family and other forms of support decreased substantially after treatment end, one in four parents stated a need for psychological support (20%).⁴

Support by the extended family, especially grandparents and friends, is an important source regarding child care and other household chores such as grocery shopping.^{24,25} Additionally, psychological interventions and support groups have been associated with lower parental distress and higher post-traumatic growth.²⁶

Conclusion. Our third study showed that gender differences regarding PTSS were only present among parents.³ PTSS did not differ in men and women without children. Gender differences may be explained by the distribution of family roles, especially in the context of caring for a child with a chronic health condition. While most of parents of childhood cancer survivors seem to recover from the childhood cancer experience, a small proportion may benefit from ongoing support. Facilitating access to psychosocial services could potentially benefit all parents who have a child with chronic illness.

IMPLICATIONS

Additional support. While tailored psycho-oncology services have become an integral part of treatment in the context of childhood cancer²⁷, we have shown that some parents report a need for support after treatment end, especially psychosocial.^{4,28} It is important to keep in mind that in clinical practice an individualized approach is key to a successful intervention. Population means are likely not meaningful to the individual who is suffering as a result of a challenging experience. We can not extrapolate from the population average – which

for instance shows no elevated risk for PTSS – to the individual who has responded on the maximum range of the scale and is likely in need for adequate support. For instance, parents of survivors who still accompany survivors to LTFU-clinics (who are a subset of all affected parents) have reported the same levels of PTSS as parents of children on active cancer treatment.²¹ Parents that accompany survivors to LTFU-care reported higher unresolved feelings of anger, sorrow and loss associated with the illness experience than parents of children on active treatment.²¹ There is a large body of evidence demonstrating that psychosocial interventions can be effective in supporting the psychological reaction of families across many different types of pediatric injury and illnesses.²⁹

The integrative model of Paediatric Medical Traumatic Stress (PMTS) (embraced for study 3) outlines the current evidence for successful strategies regarding intervention for paediatric patients and their parents, to support families' coping with unresolved anger and sorrow associated with the illness experience.^{21,29} It further outlines opportunities for repeated screening and assessment to monitor psychological outcomes. Trauma-informed care includes ensuring that psychosocial services are well integrated into the medical care; including psychoeducation to inform parents about common psychological reactions when having a sick child, along with information regarding referral pathways in the event that psychological symptoms do develop over time.³⁰

Similarly, the Family-System Illness model (FIS)^{31,32}, which was embraced for the *Cascade* intervention study (in which study 2 was taking place³³), advocates for a range of family-based therapy-approaches that take into account the child's and family's individual situation and family-system. The model is useful in guiding clinical practitioners with a psychosocial map to support families in normalizing and contextualising their experiences. For example, using family consultations, psychosocial check-ups, brief interventions, cognitive-behavioural therapies, and psychoeducational multi-family groups.³¹

Providing continued psychosocial support for parents after treatment end is promising; not only to improve parents' personal health and well-being, but also to empower them in their parenting. Parental distress can negatively affect survivors, for example increase survivors' psychological suffering and distress or lower their school performance.³⁴⁻³⁶ Maternal emotional warmth was associated with fewer life-time diagnosis of anxiety and depression in adult survivors.³⁷ Increased family functioning has been associated with positive outcomes in childhood cancer patients and their siblings.³⁸ Hence, improving psychosocial care for parents of childhood

cancer survivors not only promotes their well-being and quality of life, but is also likely to have a positive impact on the entire family system.

FUTURE RESEARCH & CHALLENGES

Gender & roles. Future studies recruiting both parents are needed to gain further insights into their dyadic experiences, role distributions, and combined coping efforts, relative to caring for a child with a chronic illness and its associated psychosocial consequences for caregivers, such as PTSS or anxiety. Additional studies investigating differences in parenting strategies and coping-styles in relation to the family roles are needed, because they may imply different support needs.³⁹⁻⁴¹

Translational research. We have long-standing evidence that psychological support can be successful in supporting families during difficult times, such as chronic illness.^{29,42} Just recently, the SNSF has communicated its priorities to enhance the value of research for the society, which included bringing universities together with institutions to shorten the time it takes to transfer scientific findings into practice.⁴³ Psychological sciences have a long tradition in translating their research into practice.⁴⁴ It remains important to conduct translational research studies that assess acceptability, feasibility, efficacy, and further assess mechanisms of change as well as the clinical utility of interventions.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ A bidirectional flow of information from research to practice and back is fundamental to understand and improve the interventions directed at improving mental health outcomes.⁴⁸ To foster the translation from research to practice, it is also crucial to involve key stakeholders from early on in the process.⁴⁵ Partners in the community settings who are key in the uptake of interventions in real life (e.g. survivor and parents organisations), the precise clinical context(s) where interventions will be incorporated in the future, and readiness for change, will need to be carefully considered. A vast variety of support services exist, but there is mixed evidence for their efficacy across different intervention types and studies.²⁹ It is likely that individuals respond differently to various forms of intervention based on personal preferences.

A life course approach seems warranted to better understand the complex interplays. Recent systematic reviews in paediatric illness highlighted the need to adopt a developmental lens and to further understand the biological and socio-ecological interplays with mental health.^{29,49} The components of the family-system, biological and environmental characteristics are interconnected and an improvement in one outcome signifies at the same time improvement in the entire framework, and as such, a success in addressing public health

challenges.^{34,50} As outlined at the *Swiss Public Health Conference 2019 on Child and Adolescent Public Health*, actions are needed, including implementation science, e-health interventions and engaging schools, to improve overall population health and quality of life.⁵¹⁻⁵³ With every parent who is able to cope more adaptively, we may improve the outcome of the whole family-system.¹⁷

E-mental health interventions through video-conferencing technologies, or self-management, and interventions using artificial intelligence have demonstrated similar efficacy in improving psychological outcomes, such as anxiety, depression, or PTSS, as face to face interventions.^{34,54} A recent systematic review showed that e-mental health interventions using trauma-focused and non-trauma focused cognitive-behavioral therapy, and also all other therapy modalities, showed significant improvements in PTSS as compared to comparison groups.⁵⁵ Such interventions may be especially helpful in reducing barriers to participate because of their timely and location-independent access, as well as increased perception of privacy.^{56,57} In particular, the online format has also been seen to help overcome the stigma around mental health.⁵⁶

However, there are still important barriers to address for such interventions. For instance, therapists were seen to be hesitant and sceptic towards the videoconferencing interventions, more so than client themselves.^{57,58} Although the studies suggest that psychologists usually adjust to this new format in a short period of time, it will be important to document the small adjustments they make in their communication styles and associated outcomes such as therapeutic alliance.^{57,58} Furthermore, appropriate risk assessment and management will need to be carefully planned and included in programs to avoid adverse outcomes. Additionally, artificial intelligence bears the potential for personalized therapy plans informed through neuroscience.⁵⁹

Lack of resources. Many psychosocial characteristics are modifiable and can improve given there is sufficient support, for instance in form of psychosocial counselling, cognitive-behavioural and/or psychotherapy, which is a robust rationale for allocating more funding to psychosocial resources. Multidisciplinary LTFU-clinics that included mental-health assessments were seen to be feasible and help to address survivors' needs.⁴ However, their feasibility depended so far on the intrinsic motivation of local teams and on financial commitment from third parties, because essential parts of the work are not covered by health insurances.⁴

In Switzerland, there is a lack of funding and human resources to tackle the challenges of multidisciplinary LTFU-care, especially regarding psychosocial counselling (for instance for fatigue, or academic/vocational

aspirations).⁶⁰ In Australia, the same challenges have been described, with inadequate funding for clinics and research⁶¹, appealing to philanthropic money.⁶¹ Funding was seen as a growing priority to allow further screenings and support services as the population is growing but there is understaffing and limited clinic space.⁶¹

Health-care professionals play a crucial role for positive health-care experiences of parents and survivors long into survivorship. It is important to keep in mind that with the growing population and expanding services offered, delegating to and involving other specialists (e.g. for psychosocial screenings) remains important to minimise the burden on health-care professionals and health-care systems running already at full capacity.

REFERENCES – REFLECTION 3

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3. STRENGTHS & LIMITATIONS

The most important strengths and limitations of the individual studies composing this thesis have been presented and discussed in their respective publications. Therefore, I allow myself to focus in this section on just a few general strengths and limitations of the overall work contributing to this doctoral thesis.

3.1 STRENGTHS

Population-based samples. A fundamental strength of all three studies is the use of a population-based approach to recruit survivors and their parents. Another strength is the relatively high participation rates considering the long time since diagnosis and extensive questionnaires to fill out for long-term survivors and parents (studies 1 & 3), and the high time-commitment needed for parents participating in the group-based e-mental health intervention (study 2).

Theory-informed research. Study 1 and study 3 were both informed through frameworks with long-standing evidence and application in research – the *Theory of Planned Behavior*², and the integrative model of *Paediatric Medical Traumatic Stress*.^{2,3} For study 2, no model in the health-care communication experience in the context of childhood cancer existed, so I used *Grounded-Theory*, a hypothesis-generating approach within qualitative health psychology – to develop such a model to apply and test in future research and practice. Another important quality of the present doctoral thesis is the transparent reporting and reflection on the epistemological stance, and how those affected the research's findings.

Interdisciplinary collaborations. A major strength of this thesis further includes the interdisciplinary collaborations with relevant hospital-sites, the *Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry*, health-care professionals, and the integration as PhD candidate in multidisciplinary research teams. Furthermore, all projects that resulted in a study in this thesis involved key stakeholders at important milestones of the projects, such as for example patients, patient associations, and community organisations in the development of the questionnaires, and in the design and implementation of the intervention study *Cascade*.

Novel research. The studies included in this study investigated timely research questions which encountered a lot of resonance in the field, at conferences, and through twitter. The *Parents-Study* is one of the few to address questions on psychosocial well-being among parents of very long-term survivors, and to systematically recruit

both, mothers and fathers – resulting in a distribution of participating genders similar to those seen in general populations (i.e. ca. 60% female, ca. 40% male). Furthermore, the *Parents-Study* encompassed a complex, randomized study-design to investigate a potential reporting-bias called “focussing-illusion”.⁴ The *Cascade* study in turn has its key strength in using novel video-conferencing technologies and in delivering the intervention under the umbrella of a randomized-controlled trial. The Australian research group is known to develop evidence-based based resources quickly and effectively, using implementation science to foster the uptake of such resources into clinical care.

And last but not least, this thesis covered a wide range of relevant topics in the context of childhood cancer, applying appropriate and advanced methodological skills to answer the research questions (e.g. structural equation modelling, grounded theory, multilevel modelling).

3.2 LIMITATIONS

Recruitment. An important limitation of both, the Swiss and Australian studies, among parents of childhood cancer survivors is that unfortunately it was not possible to know the exact sample size of parents who were approached to participate in the studies, which was due to the logistics of the recruiting sites (study 2) and study design (study 3).

Furthermore, there might be a self-selection bias into the studies, which could result in a under- or overestimation of outcomes: Either mostly survivors/parents who were motivated/interested and who are well enough to participate could have self-selected into the studies; or on the other hand, those who were particularly unwell might have self-selected into the studies, such that problems might be under or overestimated respectively. Possibly, it could have been insightful to insist, and follow-up on, reasons for refusals during recruitment.

Self-reported measures are essential in psychological research and when physiological measurements are unavailable. However, particular attention should be drawn to the way we assessed “having a child with chronic illness” in the *Parents-Study*. We asked parents whether they had a child with chronic illness – the response format was “yes” or “no”, and an open question where parents could indicate the chronic condition. A quick sighting of this data shows that the indicated illnesses represent a very wide range of physical and mental health conditions. To name a few: hay fever, food allergies, neurodermatitis, asthma, back problems, ear

malformation, endometriosis, multiple sclerosis, renal transplantation, substance addiction, depression, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, epilepsy, autism, trisomie 21.

Given that prior research suggests the psychological impact of the disease, for example PTSS, is primarily predicted by the cognitive appraisal of the situation^{2,3,5}, and not the medical diagnosis *per se*, this should not interfere with the overall conclusions of our findings. However, in future studies it would be interesting to investigate how parents appraise those conditions, for instance, using the *Brief Illness Perception Questionnaire*.⁶ Qualitative studies examining the impact of those conditions on parents' daily living in detail could further contribute to identify important context information, health beliefs, and meanings for the individual and the family-system. Hence, future mixed-methods studies could be valuable to shed further light on the embodied-societo-psychological interplays.

A further limitation of self-reported measures are the recall and social desirability bias. Survivors and their parents have gone through a highly stressful time. Consequently, their impression of past events, such as interactions with health-care professionals, might have changed over time. For example, parents' satisfaction with care was seen to be associated with the positive outcome of treatment.^{7,8} Parental self-report of treatment and diagnosis (which we had to use in study 2) might also compromise data quality in those variables, due to their complexity, and difficulty to recall those details. Certain questions might further be prone to a social desirability bias, such as education or declaration of income.

Treatment type. In all three studies, we included treatment type in a hierarchical manner. Namely, we included individuals with "surgery only" as reference category, individuals having received chemotherapy (and may have had surgery) were coded as level 1, those having received radiotherapy (may have had surgery and/or radiotherapy) as level 2, and those treated with stem cell transplantation (may have had surgery and/or chemotherapy, and/or radiotherapy) coded level 3. The level of detail in this treatment variable might be insufficient to detect associations between treatment type and outcomes of interest, such as LTFU-attendance or PTSS. However, for sufficient statistical power for the analysis, it is important to group similar types of treatment into categories. Perhaps, including treatment variables that reflect the *burden of treatment* rather than treatment type, for instance how long the treatment period lasted, how many doses of treatment were necessary, and/or how invasive those procedures were would be useful. Yet, again, perceived level of threat by survivors and parents might be more predictive of their psychosocial adjustment to the experience rather than these objective indicators. Perhaps if we want to assess the direct impact of treatment on psychological

outcomes, we would need to include measures during treatment procedures which related to how the treatment was appraised and experienced.

Association is not causation. Another important limitation is that with the designs from study 1-3, it is impossible to draw any conclusions of the directionality of the association. Unfortunately, with a retrospective design, we are unable to draw conclusions on causation. Hence, more longitudinal studies are needed to observe mechanisms of change and their determinants.

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4. RESEARCH FINDINGS IN PERSPECTIVE

In this section I will briefly discuss a few considerations regarding my research, namely regarding external validity (i.e. cautions with the conclusions of this study for other populations) and its potential for applicability (i.e. implementation, processes-oriented) and transferability (i.e. effectiveness, outcome-oriented) for other contexts.

4.1 EXTERNAL VALIDITY

Non-Western culture. First of all, the presented studies have been conducted in Western, high-income countries. Contextual factors, such as cultural aspects, are underpinning social norms, attitudes, health behaviors, the way illness is conceptualized and managed, and parental engagement in (health-)care. For instance, an article highlighting the experiences among Arab families outlined that there is the impression that health-care professionals will not disclose the truth about diagnosis and prognosis, and that they often do not want to disclose the bad news to children, aiming to protect them from fear.¹ Furthermore, parents' beliefs, traditions, religion and socio-economic factors are impacting parents priorities and needs.¹

Moreover, there is a huge gap in progress regarding early detection, treatment, patient education, and dealing with consequences of cancer between high-income and low- to middle-income countries.^{2,3} Future challenges include closing this gap, and will need careful considerations of transferability in light – for example – of differing cultural aspects, and logistics of the present context.

Adolescents with cancer. This thesis focussed on childhood cancer survivors and their parents. The experiences for adolescent and young adult cancer survivors and their parents might vary as a function of their developmental stage and maturity. For instance, we have seen that for adolescent and young adult cancer survivors attitudes regarding the LTFU-care were associated with the intention to attend LTFU-care⁴, whereas childhood cancer survivors' attitudes were not associated with intention. Parents of adolescent and young adult survivors may also face different types of challenges in supporting their children regarding treatment. For example, in finding the right amount of balance between supporting their autonomy and self-management of the treatment or LTFU-care and being an authority figure (i.e. shared management).^{5,6} Furthermore, parental worry and psychological impact may also depend on age or stage of maturity their adolescent or adult child is when it becomes ill.

Bereaved parents were not included in all three studies of this thesis. While the experiences of parents of children with cancer does not seem to depend on the exact diagnosis the child has received, it has been shown that the experiences of parents of survivors and bereaved parents differ.⁷ Bereaved parents display an ongoing substantial emotional burden several years after their child's death. For instance, they display higher PTSS than parents of survivors.⁸ Additional research is needed to better understand the consequences for parents of bereaved children.

4.2 APPLICABILITY & TRANSFERABILITY

Our research is likely informative for other fields that address other chronic health conditions or rare diseases, such as sickle-cell disease, cystic fibrosis, epilepsy, or congenital heart disease. There are many similarities in the challenges that arise among affected children, parents, and family-systems. In the following, I have chosen one example to illustrate the potential for applicability and transferability of my findings to another setting: Congenital heart disease (CHD).

CHD is the most common birth defect worldwide.⁹ The population is rapidly growing, with almost 90% of children now surviving into adulthood in high-income countries such as Switzerland, called CHD-survivors.¹⁰⁻¹²

LTFU-care. Both, childhood cancer survivors (CCS), and CHD-survivors are a growing population with specific health concerns and vulnerabilities.^{11,13} In the past decades, medical care has improved dramatically for both populations, leading to better survival and function.^{10,11,14-16} As with childhood cancer, CHD is rarely "cured" and requires long-term follow-up care, using multidisciplinary approaches and individualized treatment plans.^{17,18} Yet, a lot of CCS and CHD-survivors are lost to follow-up.^{19,20}

Health-care communication & experience. Similarities also include the challenges faced by transitioning maturing adolescents and young adults to adult centres, self-management of the health status, and psychosocial, educational and vocational needs of survivors and their families.^{21,22} Health-related parenting stress is significant for both parents of children with cancer, and parents of children with CHD.²³

Psychological consequences. Many CCS and CHD-survivors are at increased risk for neurodevelopmental deficits that may persist into adulthood.²⁴⁻²⁶ Health-related quality of life^{27,28}, body image^{29,30}, and social and family relationships³¹ may also be affected. Another similarity includes the life-threatening nature and the

necessity of aggressive and invasive treatment procedures to treat children, and thus the potentially traumatic impact on children, parents and the family-system as a whole.³²⁻³⁴

Registries for CHD have been newly established³⁵ and there is a need for more psychosocial research in this field, as survival rates have improved substantially in recent years.³⁶ Given the commonalities of the challenges faced by the two populations, it is likely that the large body of knowledge already generated in the past years within the context of childhood cancer may benefit newer research endeavours in the younger, rapidly evolving field of CHD, especially concerning long-term psychosocial consequences.

4.3 OUTLOOK

From pathogenesis to salutogenesis.³⁷ In this thesis the studies' aims primarily focused on aspects that "do not work" and disease prevention, namely embraced a rather pathogenic perspective in order to find avenues for improvement, for example in identifying risk factors.³⁸ Many survivors of childhood cancer and their families report that the cancer experience has impacted them in positive ways.⁷ It will be important to draw attention to concepts such as coping, resilience and post-traumatic growth in order to identify protective factors that help people deal with, and mitigate, adverse consequences. For instance, using the *Family Resilience Framework*^{39,40} or the model of *Post-traumatic Growth in Pediatric Medical Trauma*⁴¹.

Investigating the dynamics between negative and positive changes will allow us further insights into how individuals can adapt to, or overcome, the challenges of living with illness, or even grow stronger from such experiences.

Siblings & grandparents are part of the family-system too, and thus often affected by the childhood cancer experience. Siblings often feel that their family has been ripped apart, and is shifting family roles, with greater focus on the child with cancer, and changing responsibilities among all family members.⁴² Grandparents represent often an important source for emotional and instrumental support, for instance, in caring for the siblings of the child diagnosed with cancer when parents are at the hospital.⁴³ It would be strategic to collect all family member's perspective simultaneously in a single study in order to gain further insights into the interplays within the family-system when a child is diagnosed with childhood cancer. To our knowledge, no such studies yet exist. Prof Michel's upcoming research project on *Grandparents' involvement and psychological outcomes when a grandchild is diagnosed with cancer* might be among the first to address this gap.⁴⁴

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CONCLUSION

The overall goal of this thesis was to address three research gaps in the context of childhood cancer, in order to inform, and ultimately improve, the current clinical practice for childhood cancer survivors and their parents.

In the present thesis, I added to the understanding of childhood cancer survivors' LTFU-care intention and attendance, explored parents' health-care and communication experience with health-care professionals during and after their child's treatment, and described parents' long-term stress response.

For many illnesses nowadays premature death can be prevented, which leads to a growing population confronted with life-threatening and/or limiting illness and its consequences. **Optimal adherence to long-term follow-up care, positive health-care and communication experiences, as well as early detection and management of psychological consequences are going to be essential for improving population health and well-being.**

With holistic LTFU-care, for both parents and survivors, the whole family system is likely to benefit from the individual improvements in health and well-being because "*Kinderkrebs ist Familienkrebs!*" (mother of 38-year old survivor).

RESEARCH OUTPUT LIST

PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS

- First author** Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Harju E, Ansari M, Waespe N, Scheinemann K, Michel G. Post-traumatic stress in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors and parents of the Swiss general population. *Journal of Psychosocial Oncology: Research and Practice*. 2020; **2**(3), e024. doi: [10.1097/OR9.000000000000024](https://doi.org/10.1097/OR9.000000000000024)
- Baenziger J, Hetherington K, Wakefield CE, McGill BC, Carlson L, Cohn RJ, Sansom-Daly U. Understanding parents' communication experiences in childhood cancer: A qualitative exploration and model for future research. *Supportive Care in Cancer*. 2020; **28**, 4467-4476. doi: [10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-019-05270-6)
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- Co-Author** Christen S, Mader L, Baenziger J, Roser K, Schindera C, Tinner EM, Michel G. "I wish someone had once asked me how I'm doing": Support needs and disadvantages of pediatric cancer survivors' parents. *Pediatric Blood & Cancer*. 2019; **66**(8), e27767. doi: [10.1002/pbc.27767](https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.27767)
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- Baenziger J. Etude exploratoire. Devenir mère en étant porteuse d'une cardiopathie congénitale : une perspective corporo-sociéto-psychologique de l'expérience vécue. Available from: http://serval.unil.ch/?id=serval:BIB_S_00000023241

CONTRIBUTION TO DIES ACADEMICUS

- Invited Speaker** **Spätfolgen von Kinderkrebs: Psychische Auswirkungen auf die Eltern**
Baenziger J
English: 'Long-term consequences of childhood cancer: Psychological implications for parents'
Invited Speaker. Representative PhD Candidate of the Department of Health Sciences & Medicine,
 Dies Academicus, Luzerner Theater, Switzerland. [Published Slides](#).
 07/11/2019

CONTRIBUTION TO CONFERENCES

- First author** **Post-traumatic growth in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors and parents of the general population**
Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Priboi C, Sansom-Daly UM, Michel G.
 23-26/10/2019 *Poster.* 51st Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Lyon, France.
 13/09/2019 *Pitch Presentation.* 24th PanCare Meeting, Basel, Switzerland.
 04/09/2019 *Talk.* 33rd Conference of the European Health Psychology Society, Dubrovnik, Croatia.
 29/08/2019 *Talk.* Swiss Public Health Conference, Winterthur, Switzerland.
- "I grew the confidence"- The health-care and communication experience for parents of children with cancer**
Baenziger J, Hetherington K, Wakefield CE, McGill BC, Carlson L, Cohn RJ, Sansom-Daly U.
 06/09/2019 *Talk.* 33rd Conference of the European Health Psychology Society, Dubrovnik, Croatia.
 28-29/08/2019 *Poster.* Swiss Public Health Conference, Winterthur, Switzerland.
 28/03/2019 *Poster.* Cancer Survivorship Conference 2019, Flinders Centre for Innovation in Cancer, Clinical Oncology Society of Australia, Sydney, Australia.
 23/11/2018 *Poster.* Kids Cancer Alliance Early Career Research Showcase, Cancer Institute New South Wales, Sydney, Australia.
- Post-traumatic stress symptoms in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors and the general population**
Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Harju E, Ansari M, Waspe N, Scheinemann K, Michel G.
 31/10/2018 *Talk.* International Psycho-Oncology Society (IPOS), Hong Kong, China.
 14-16/06/2018 *Poster.* Australian & New Zealand Children's Haematology/Oncology Group (ANZCHOG) Scientific Meeting, Sydney, Australia.
 04/10/2017 *Talk.* 20th PanCare Meeting, Lübeck, Germany.
- Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance of childhood cancer survivors?**
Baenziger J, Roser K, Mader L, Christen S, Tinner EM, Kuehni CE, Michel G.
 02/09/2017 *Talk.* 31st Conference of the European Health Psychology Society, Padova, Italy.
 05/05/2017 *Talk.* 19th PanCare Meeting, Lund, Sweden.
 19/10/2016 *Talk.* 48th Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Dublin, Ireland.
 22-23/09/2016 *Poster.* 5th European Symposium on Late Complications after Childhood Cancer (ESLCCC), Copenhagen, Denmark.
 3/06/2016 *Talk.* Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group (SPOG) Scientific Meeting 2016, Bern, Switzerland.
- Being different and becoming normal: Pregnancy and motherhood of women with congenital heart disease**
Baenziger J, de Stoutz N, Fasseur F.
 23-27/08/2016 *Poster.* 30th Conference of the European Health Psychologist Society (EHPS), Aberdeen, Scotland.
 18/03/16 *Talk.* Scientific Meeting of the Association for European and Paediatric Congenital Cardiology (AEPC), Rotterdam, Netherlands.
- Last author** **Post-traumatic growth, resilience and coping in family members of childhood cancer survivors – A systematic review**
Halldorsdottir B, Michel G, Baenziger J.
 02/09/2020 *Talk.* Swiss Public Health Conference 2020. Lucerne, Switzerland – online conference (COVID-19).

CONTRIBUTION TO CONFERENCES (continued)**Co-author Changing family and social relationships: Adolescents and young adult cancer survivors' perspectives**

Hayes T, Sansom-Daly U, Kelada L, [Baenziger J](#), Hetherington K., Cohn RJ, Holland L, Plaster M, and Wakefield CE.

09-12/06/2020 *Poster.* AIFS 2020 Conference, Australian Institute of Family Studies, Melbourne, Australia.

Psychosocial distress in parents of very long-term childhood cancer survivors

Michel G. [Baenziger J](#), Roser K.

23-26/10/2019 *Poster.* 51st Annual Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Lyon, France.

26/04/2019 *Talk.* 23rd PanCare Meeting, Opatija, Croatia.

Relationship status and quality of partner relationship among parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors

Mader L, Roser K, [Baenziger J](#), Scheinmann K, Michel G.

16/11/2018 *Talk.* International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Kyoto, Japan.

Impact of physical appearance changes reported by adolescent and young adult cancer survivors: A qualitative analysis

Brierly M-E, Sansom-Daly U, [Baenziger J](#), Wakefield CE.

10-11/10/2018 *Poster.* Sydney Cancer Conference - Bridging research and practice, Sydney, Australia.

Supportive needs of pediatric cancer survivors' parents

Christen C, Mader L, [Baenziger J](#), Roser K, Schindera C, Tinner EM, Michel G.

19/04/2018 *Talk.* 21st PanCare Meeting, Prague, Czech Republic.

Health-related quality of life in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors

***Abstract nominated for Young Investigator Award, presenting author Julia Baenziger*

Roser K, [Baenziger J](#), Mader L, Harju E, Michel G.

23-26/10/2019 ***Talk.* 51st Annual Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Lyon, France.

4/10/2017 *Talk.* 20th PanCare Meeting, Lübeck, Germany.

Follow-up care attendance in survivors of adolescent and young adult cancer: implementation of the Theory of Planned Behaviour

Roser K, [Baenziger J](#), Mader L, Christen S, Michel G.

20/10/2016 *Talk.* 48th Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Dublin, Ireland.

22-23/09/2016 *Poster.* 5th European Symposium on Late Complications after Childhood Cancer (ESLCCC), Copenhagen, Denmark.

Household income and risk-of-poverty of parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors

Mader L, Roser K, [Baenziger J](#), Michel G.

22-23/09/2016 *Poster.* 5th European Symposium on Late Complications after Childhood Cancer (ESLCCC), Copenhagen, Denmark.

Education, employment and marriage in survivors of teenage and young adult cancer

Mader L, Christen S, Roser K, [Baenziger J](#), Michel G.

20/10/2016 *Poster.* 48th Congress of the International Society of Paediatric Oncology (SIOP), Dublin, Ireland.

OUTREACH ACTIVITIES**18/08/2020 Inspiring Mothers in Academia iMA Roundtable**

Organizer & Facilitator. Finding balance in motherhood & research, University of Lucerne, CH.

10/09/2019 Poster Workshop of the 2nd PanCare Educational Day

Facilitator. 24th PanCare Meeting, University of Basel, CH.

11/06/2019 Twitter Talk: How to use social media to promote your research

Presentation to peer researchers at the University of Lucerne, CH.

20/05/2019 Knowledge translation: Experiences from an SNF doc.mobility fellowship

Presentation at the PhD Research Seminar in Health Sciences, University of Lucerne, CH.

23/01/2019 Theories & Models in Health Psychology

Presentation at the seminar of the Behavioural Sciences Unit, Kids Cancer Centre, Sydney, AUS.

Can the Theory of Planned Behavior help explain follow-up attendance of childhood cancer survivors?

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Introduction

- Regular **long-term follow-up care** is important to monitor health.
- Many Swiss childhood cancer survivors **do not attend** follow-up care.¹

Theoretical Framework

- The **Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)** was developed to predict a diverse range of health behaviors (cf. Model in Figure 3.).²

Aims

Using the framework of the Theory of Planned Behavior we aimed to:

- Identify **predictors for the intention** to attend follow-up care
- Examine **association between intention and actual attendance**.

Results: TPB & Follow-up Attendance

- Current follow-up attendance: **145 (48.8%)**
- High intention to attend follow-up: **148 (50.1%)**

Figure 3. SEM and LR of follow-up care attendance according to the TPB

Aim i)

- Model shows reasonably **good fit** (SRMR = 0.05 ; CFI = 0.97; RMSEA = 0.09)
 - Social Norm** was associated with higher intention (coef = 0.89, $p < 0.001$)
 - Attitude (coef = 0.07, $p = 0.37$) and perceived control (coef = 0.04, $p = 0.53$) were not associated with intention
- Model **explained 89.7% of the variance in intention** to follow-up care

Aim ii)

- Higher **intention** (OR= 2.1, 95% CI: 1.8 – 2.4) & **perceived control** (OR=1.3, 95% CI: 1.0 – 1.6) were **positively associated** with attendance

Methods

Population

- Swiss childhood cancer survivors
- diagnosed with cancer aged <16 years, after 1990
- aged ≥ 18 years at study, ≥ 5 years since diagnosis

Data collection

- Questionnaire to 716 eligible survivors
- 3 predictors** (attitude, subjective social norm, & perceived behavioral control) & **intention** (7-point Likert scale)
- Attendance** (Yes/No)

Analysis

i) Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

- Attitudes (5 items)
 - e.g. *I find regular follow-up meaningful-superfluous*
 - Subjective social norms (2 items)
 - e.g. *Most people that are important to me think I should attend to follow-up care*
 - Perceived behavioral control (2 items)
 - e.g. *For me, to attend regular follow up is easy-complicated*
- Intention (2 items)
e.g. *I intend to attend follow-up next year*

ii) Logistic regression (LR)

- Intention
 - Perceived Behavioral Control
- Attendance

Results: Participants

- 299 survivors**
- 166 females (55.5%)

Figure 1. Most frequent diagnoses.

Figure 2. Treatment types.

Means:

- age at study: **25.1 years**
- age at diagnosis: **8.3 years**
- time since diagnosis: **16.3 years**

Discussion

- Limitations:** low response rate (41,8%)
- Strengths:** similar results in Swiss adolescent and young adult cancer survivors

Practical Implications

- Promotional interventions** to increase intention for and actual follow-up attendance should focus on **improving supportive social norms** and **enhance perceived control**.
- A next step is to **raise awareness** among **health professionals, families and friends** on the importance of their support regarding the survivor's follow-up care.
- Perceived control may be increased by providing the survivor with **information on the different models** for follow-up care.

Conclusion

- Parents, doctors and medical staff may play a crucial role** in underlining the importance of regular follow-up care.

♥ Thank You ♥

SPOG & Survivors

Funding Sources:

Swiss National Science Foundation Ambizione grant No. PZ00P3_121682/1 PZ00P3-141722 to GM
 Swiss Cancer League grant No. KLS-3412-02-2014.

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References

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²Ajzen, I. (2013). *Theory of Planned Behavior Questionnaire*. Measurement Instrument Database for the Social Science. Retrieved from www.mids.us

CAN THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR HELP EXPLAIN FOLLOW-UP ATTENDANCE OF CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVORS?

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Introduction Background

- ♥ Incidence rate: 16 per 100'000 *Swiss Cancer Report 2015*
 - ♥ >80% survive *Schindler et al. 2017*
 - ♥ High risk for late effects & second cancer *Hudson et al. 2013*
 - Auditory
 - Pulmonary
 - Endocrine
 - Cardiac
 - Neurocognitive
 - ♥ >66% chronic health condition *Phillips et al. 2015*
- Regular long-term follow-up care is important!

Image source: <https://www.popsugar.com/moms/Childhood-Cancer-Survivor-Photos-34819602>

Introduction Background

- ♥ Lack of attendance to follow-up care *Zheng et al. 2016, Michel et al. 2010*
- ♥ Factors associated with attendance
 - Cancer related *Zheng et al. 2016, Barakat et al. 2012, Michel et al. 2010*
 - Socio-demographic *Nathan et al. 2016, Barakat et al. 2012*

Introduction Aims

- ♥ Theory of Planned Behavior

- 1) Investigate predictors for the intention to attend follow-up
- 2) Examine associations between intention and attendance

Methods Population & Procedure

- ♥ Swiss childhood cancer survivor study (baseline)
 - Registered in the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry
 - Swiss residency at diagnosis
 - Diagnosed <16 years
 - Survived ≥5 years
- ♥ Follow-up questionnaire
 - 18+ years at study
 - Diagnosis after 1990

Methods Theory of planned behavior

Results Population

- 299 survivors (response rate 41.8%)
- 166 females (55.5%)

Results Intention & Attendance

	Years	95% CI
Mean age at study	25.1	24.6, 25.6
Mean age at diagnosis	8.3	7.8, 8.9
Mean time since diagnosis	16.3	15.8, 16.7

- High intention: 151 (51.5%)
- Attendance: 145 (48.5%)

Results Theory of planned behavior

Good fit (SRMR = 0.067 ; CFI = 0.956; RMSEA = 0.07)

Discussion Limitations & Strength

- Relatively low response rate (41.8%)
- Females and with more complex treatment more likely to respond

- Population-based sample
- Similar results in Swiss adolescent and young adult cancer survivors

Discussion Practical Implications

Promotional interventions:

Improve supportive social norm

- Raise awareness among health care professionals, partners, families and friends on the importance of their support
- Expressing expectations

Enhance perceived control

- Send out invitations for follow-up care
- Survivorship Passport
- Provide easily accessible follow-up clinics
- Provide Choice & Flexibility

Discussion Conclusion

- To increase attendance, parents, partners, friends, and health care professionals need to express that they support the survivor in attending follow-up care and underline its importance.

Acknowledgements

We kindly thank Survivors & the Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group

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Funding Sources

Swiss National Science Foundation
Swiss Cancer League

krebsliga schweiz
ligue suisse contre le cancer
lega svizzera contro il cancro

FONDS NATIONAL SUISSE
SCHWEIZERISCHER NATIONALFONDS
FONDO NAZIONALE SVIZZERO
SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance?

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Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance?

Attitude	n	Mean	(SD)
<i>I find regular follow-up...</i>			
A1 meaningful–superfluous	268	5.96	1.44
A2 good–bad	293	5.96	1.72
A3 pleasant–unpleasant	263	4.32	1.88
A4 interesting–boring	264	4.98	1.91
A5 important–unimportant	294	6.62	1.00
<i>To me, to detect and treat possible late effects of my cancer early</i>			
Subjective norm			
SN1 Most people that are important to me think I should attend to follow-up care.			
very true–not true at all	293	4.37	2.57
It is expected from me that I will attend follow-up regularly.			
SN2 very true–not true at all	294	3.73	2.53
Perceived Control			
For me, attending regular follow up is			
PC1 easy–complicated	282	5.23	1.74
PC2 not at all stressful–stressful	273	4.91	1.91
It is foremost in my hands whether I regularly attend follow-up or			
PC3 very true–not true at all	294	5.64	1.89
Intention			
I1 I intend to attend follow-up next year			
very true–not true at all	295	4.25	2.74
It is probable that I will attend follow-up within the next year.			
I2 very true–not true at all	292	4.25	2.72
Attendance			
	n	Coded as	
1 I regularly attend follow-up.	124	Yes	
2 I irregularly attend follow-up.	21	Yes	
3 Follow-up is completed but I visit my treating doctor when I have questions.	38	No	
4 Follow-up is completed and I never visit my former treating doctor.	114	No	

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance?

Discussion Interpretation

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance?

Discussion Interpretation

Can the theory of planned behavior help explain follow-up attendance?

«I grew the confidence»

The health-care and communication experience for parents of children with cancer

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Introduction

- Following their child's cancer diagnosis, parents have to rapidly familiarize themselves with cancer-specific information and the health-care setting.
- Previous studies have stated a need for theory to help address parents' difficulties when navigating the health care system.¹

Aim

We examined **parents' experiences with health care professionals (HCPs)** to better understand the health-care and communication experience during and after their child's cancer treatment.

Methods

Population

Parents of **children aged <18 years** who recently completed cancer treatment with curative intent from **8 Australian hospitals**.

Data collection

- In-depth telephone interviews using the *Psychosocial Adjustment to Illness Scale*²
- Part of the baseline assessment of the 'Cascade' survivorship intervention³

Analysis

We used grounded theory to explore parents' health care experiences.

Parents' & Survivors' Characteristics

58 Parents of survivors

- 52 mothers and 6 fathers, mean age 40.1 years [range 20-55]
- Average age of child at diagnosis: 5.1 [0-15] years
- Time since treatment: 1.9 [0.3-10.7] years

Results

i. Key findings

- Parents **greatly appreciated HCP's skills and support** (informational, practical, emotional)
- Parents **rationalized negative interactions** by the limiting circumstances of the medical environment.
- A majority of parents **felt detached** from the health care system and professionals **after treatment ended**.

ii. Themes & Model

Parents **built trust** in the working relationship with HCPs, based on their attitudes and interactions.
Parents' degree of trust in HCPs **influenced the way they engaged** in their child's health-care.

Discussion

We propose a new framework explaining potential mechanisms in parents' health care communication-experience.

Limitation: potential sampling and recall bias

Strengths: indirect assessment of communication experience; first study to explore the parent-HCP communication in Australia

Practical Implications

- HCP who were **approachable and personable** seemed to gain parents' trust more easily.
- Transparency through **continuous communication** to mitigate treatment uncertainty.
- Explicit and **well-explained guidance**, e.g. in form of tailored survivorship care plans, might benefit parents' engagement in long-term follow-up care

Conclusion

Maintaining contact, and acknowledging survivors' continuous needs, was essential to parents' positive experiences throughout treatment and after treatment ended.

Acknowledgements

- Heartfelt thank you to everyone involved in this study, and above all the parents for sharing their experiences and time!
- Funding: This project is supported by a Cancer Council NSW Program Grant PG16-02 with the support of the Estate of the Late Harry McPaul.
- Julia Baenziger is supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation Grant P1LUP1_178330 and P1LUP1_178330/1.

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THE HEALTH CARE & COMMUNICATION EXPERIENCE FOR PARENTS OF CHILDREN WITH CANCER

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Background Childhood Cancer

- **Leading cause of death** after accidents in children
Kyu et al. 2016
- **> 18'000 children** diagnosed each year in Europe
American Childhood Cancer Org. 2019
- **10-year survival >87%**
Pfeiffer et al. 2017

Background Health Care & Communication

- **New environment:** health-care setting
- **Medical jargon:** cancer-specific information
- **Misunderstandings:** conflicts
- **Dealing with late effects & secondary cancer**

Coyne et al. 2014; Davies, Salmon, & Young 2017; Fuertes et al. 2017; Hoekstra-Weebers et al. 2001; Vetsch et al. 2016

Background Australian Context

- **Geographical dispersion**
- **Few specialist oncology centres**
- **Large distance to travel**

Background Aim

- **Research Gap**
 - **Need for theory to address parents difficulties**
Davies, Salmon, & Young 2017
- **Aim**
 - **Parents' experiences with health care professionals (HCPs)**
 - **To better understand the health-care & communication experience**
 - **During and after their child's cancer treatment**

Methods Population & Procedure

- **Parents of**
 - Children aged <18 years
 - Children completed treatment with curative intent
- **In-depth telephone interviews**
 - Psychosocial adjustment to illness scale
Morrow, Chiarello, & Derogatis 1987
 - Semi-structured clinical interview

Methods Framework

- **Grounded Theory**
Glaser & Strauss 1967
 - Software Nvivo 12.0
 - Iterative analysis, discussion of emerging themes, memos,...
 - Double coding & inter-rater reliability
- **Critical & co-constructivist perspective**
 - Interaction social, physical, & psychological
 - Reflection on preconceptions, background, ...

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

7/18

Results Participants

- **58 parents: 52 mothers & 6 fathers**

Child's Cancer Diagnosis

Child's Treatment

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

8/18

Results Model

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EHPS 2019

9/18

RESPONSIVE

"We felt very comfortable with the treatment that they were doing, because we felt confident in the staff and in their answering our questions."

LACKING GUIDANCE

"now all of a sudden you're on your own and nobody seems to care"

Interactions

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

10/18

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

11/18

EXPERTISE

"He is so knowledgeable and so experienced. You knew, whatever his recommendation was that was the best. We had such a belief in him and trust in him, and that was just key for us"

UNCERTAINTY

"going on the clinical trial was really scary cause [sic]... for me it kind of felt like they were using my kid as a trial, you know as a mice, testing out medication"

Attitudes

"I grew the confidence [sic] and I was very happy with what they were telling me and what they were doing with her"

"we have felt let down by the medical people we had dealt before because they have given us the wrong information. We have gone through this huge emotional roller coaster of awfulness."

Trust

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

11/18

Baenziger Julia

EHPS 2019

12/18

Engagement

PROACTIVE
"He nearly was given a fatal dose of chemotherapy, ... the nurse had gotten it wrong so that's why I was always there to know what was going on"

MANAGING INFORMATION NEEDS
"I read more about [the diagnosis] and I spoke to people about it. A lot of it I had to initiate myself"

FOLLOW-UP CARE
"it doesn't feel like it's an ongoing thing"

RATIONALIZING
"you've got nurses who are overworked and doing double shifts and doctors who write like, I couldn't even read it myself"

Discussion Summary

- Overall positive
 - Careful explanations
 - Participative
 - Responsive
- Negative experiences
 - Rationalizing
 - Meaning making
 - Ineffective?
 - Lacking guidance
 - High loss to follow-up rates?

Discussion Limitations & Strengths

- ~ Sampling bias
- ~ Recall bias
- ~ Sampling bias
- ~ Recall bias
- ~ Few fathers

- ✓ Indirect assessment of communication experience
- ✓ 'Naive' researcher
- ✓ First study in Australia
- ✓ Model for research & practice

Discussion Clinical Implications

- Approachable & personable
- Continuous communication
- Well-explained guidance for long-term care

Study Conclusions

Maintaining contact, and acknowledging survivors' continuous needs, was essential to parents' positive experiences throughout treatment and after treatment ended.

Acknowledgements

- ♥ Heartfelt thank you to parents and collaborators!
- ♥ Funding
 - This project is supported by:
 - Cancer Council NSW Program Grant PG16-02 with the support of the Estate of the Late Harry McPaul
 - Cancer Australia Grant Nr APP1065428
 - National Health and Medical Research Council Grants Nr APP1111800 & APP1143767
 - Kids Cancer Alliance
 - Kids with Cancer Foundation
 - Swiss National Science Foundation Grant P1LUP1_178330

it's childhood cancer awareness month
GO GOLD FOR SEPTEMBER!

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Post-traumatic stress in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors

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Introduction

The cancer experience may affect parents' psychological well-being lifelong
 → Distress, anxiety, depression¹, post-traumatic stress symptoms (PTSS)²

Post-traumatic Stress Symptoms

PTSS circumscribe the psychological reaction following a potentially traumatic event, which typically includes three different groups of symptoms:

If those symptoms are frequent and persist for longer than six months, the reaction to the event is classified as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Aims

We aimed to ...

- i. assess reported stressful events
- ii. investigate the prevalence of PTSD & PTSD
- iii. examine the socio-demographic & cancer-related risk factors

...in childhood-cancer survivor-parents compared to control-parents

Results

i. Stressful events

ii. PTSS & PTSD

Prevalence of PTSD

Survivor-parents 4.4% Control-parents 6.6%

iii. Risk factors

Survivor-parents

- Lower education
- Migration background
- Only one child
- No partner

Control-parents

- Lower education
- Migration background
- Having a child with chronic illness
- More than one child
- Retirement

Methods

Population

- Parents of long-term Swiss childhood cancer survivors
 - diagnosed with cancer aged <16 years (years 1976 -2009)
 - survived ≥5 years, aged ≥20 years at study, currently alive

Comparison

- Parents of the Swiss General Population
 - derived from representative sample from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office
 - with children aged ≥20 years

Data collection

- Questionnaire survey
- Cancer-related characteristics from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry

We measured parents' reaction to a self-reported stressful event using the Impact of Event Scale-Revised.³

Analysis → t-tests, chi² tests, multilevel regression modeling

Parents' & Survivors' Characteristics

Survivor-parents

- 396 mothers, 252 fathers of 450 survivors (38.1% responders)
 - age at study: 62.0 years
 - time since survivors' diagnosis: 23.9 years
 - survivor age at diagnosis: 6.7 years

Control-parents

- 225 mothers, 158 fathers of 302 households (mean age = 61.8 years)

Discussion

Decades after the childhood cancer experience, many parents of survivors report a childhood-cancer related event as the most stressful event.

- None of the cancer-related characteristics were associated with PTSS

Limitation: relatively low response rate

Strengths: population-based samples, ~ 25 years after diagnosis

Practical Implications

- Particular attention for those with an increased risk profile
- Facilitating access to resources and promoting support

Conclusions

→ Increased and continued psychosocial support may benefit survivors' long-term adjustment

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Thank You

SPoG, SCCR, and all participants!

Funding: Swiss National Science Foundation Grant Nr 100019_153268/1

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POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS IN PARENTS OF LONG-TERM CHILDHOOD CANCER SURVIVORS

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Background Childhood Cancer in Switzerland

- ~ 300 new diagnoses each year *Pfeiffer et al., 2017*
- 10-year survival >87% *Pfeiffer et al., 2017*
- Risk of late effects and secondary cancers *Hudson et al., 2015; Oeffinger, 2006*
 - > 66 % chronic health condition at 5-19 years old *Phillips et al., 2015*

Background Parents of Survivors

- High levels of distress, anxiety, depression *Wakefield, 2011; Vrijmoet-Wiersma et al., 2008*
- Post-traumatic Stress Symptoms (PTSS) *Bruce, 2006*
 - Higher in parents than survivors *Kazak et al., 2004*
 - Higher in mothers than fathers *Bruce, 2006*
 - Evidence inconclusive if higher PTSS in comparison to parents of healthy children *Barakat et al., 1997; Jurbergs, Long, Ticona, & Phipps, 2009*

→ Psychological late consequences for parents not well known

Background Aims

- Assess reported stressful events
- Investigate the prevalence of PTSS & PTSD
- Identify socio-demographic & cancer-related risk factors

→ Compare childhood-cancer survivor-parents to parents of the Swiss general population

Methods Samples

- Parents of long-term Swiss childhood cancer survivors
 - Diagnosed with cancer aged <16 years (years 1976 -2009)
 - Survived ≥5 years, aged ≥20 years at study, currently alive
 - Cancer-related characteristics from Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry
- Comparison parents
 - Representative sample of the general population (Swiss Federal Statistical Office)
 - Indicated having at least one child aged ≥20 years

Methods Measurements

- Any stressful event
- Impact of Event Scale – Revised: 22 items *Horowitz, Wilner, & Alvarez, 1979; Maercker & Schützwohl, 1998*

Reaction following a potentially traumatic event:

Results Study participants

- 663 parents of 461 childhood cancer survivors
 - 402 mothers
 - 261 fathers

Survivor's Diagnosis	
Leukemia	35.2%
Lymphoma	16.3%
CNS Tumor	13.8%
Renal Tumor	6.9%
Soft tissue sarcoma	6.2%
Other	21.6%

	Mean	SD	Range
Survivor's age [years]	31.3	6.34	21-54
Age at diagnosis [years]	7.2	4.49	0-15.8
Time since diagnosis [years]	24.6	6.92	7.5-40.7

- 391 comparison-parents
 - 230 mothers
 - 161 fathers

Results Stressful events

Results PTSS & PTSD

Levels of PTSS

Prevalence of PTSD

- 4.8% in **Survivor-parents**
- 6.7% in **Comparison-parents**

Results Risk factors

No cancer-related characteristics associated with PTSS or PTSD

↑ Intrusion, Avoidance + Hyperarousal
Compulsory schooling / Vocational training
vs University and Upper secondary education

↑ Intrusion if **child with a chronic illness**

↑ Avoidance among **parents of childhood cancer survivors** if not in partnership

Discussion

- Many parents of survivors report a **childhood-cancer related event** as the most stressful event
- Managing the **challenge as a team** may have resulted in altered strategies to deal with stressful life events
- Even if children are **already adults**, **increased symptoms** among both mothers and fathers

Discussion Clinical Implications

- Increased attention to individuals with **lower education** and those **with a chronically ill child**
- Facilitate access to counselling and support services

Discussion Limitations & Strengths

~ Cross-sectional design
~ Different tools to assess PTSS

- ✓ Population-based samples
- ✓ Long-term outcomes
- ✓ Many parent-dyads

Conclusion

- Parents of childhood cancer survivors seem to **overcome high levels of PTSS** after many years
- **Increased attention**
 - To parents with lower education
 - To parents with chronically ill child

Acknowledgements

♥ Thank You ♥

Special thanks to everyone involved!

Schweizerische Pädiatrische Onkologie Gruppe
Groupe d'OncoLogie Pédiatrique Suisse
Gruppo d'Oncologia Pediatrica Svizzera
Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group

Swiss
Childhood Cancer Registry

Funding: Swiss National Science Foundation
Grant Nr 100019_153268/1 **FNSNF**

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Parents Study Flow diagram

Survivors' characteristics	Participating parents of		Non-participating parents of		p-value
	461 survivors	766 survivors	461 survivors	766 survivors	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age at diagnosis	6.8	4.5	7.0	6.7	0.280
Time since diagnosis	23.9	6.8	24.2	7.0	0.281
	n	%	n	%	
Sex					
Female	206	44.7	432	56.4	<0.001
Male	255	55.4	334	43.6	
Diagnosis (ICCC-3)					0.231
Leukemia	159	34.5	256	33.4	
Lymphoma	76	16.5	141	18.4	
CNS tumor	63	13.7	114	14.9	
Neuroblastoma	15	3.3	40	5.2	
Retinoblastoma	13	2.8	14	1.8	
Renal tumor	33	7.2	50	6.5	
Hepatic tumor	6	1.3	4	0.5	
Bone tumor	31	6.7	31	4.1	
Soft tissue sarcoma	26	5.6	53	6.9	
Germ cell tumor	16	3.5	28	3.7	
LCH	23	5.0	35	4.6	
Treatment *					0.232
Surgery only	55	12.0	99	13.0	
Chemotherapy	250	54.4	371	48.8	
Radiotherapy	130	28.3	258	33.9	
Stem cell transplantation	25	5.4	33	4.3	
Relapse *					0.573
No	575	86.7	661	86.3	
Yes	88	13.3	105	13.7	

Abbreviations: ICC-3, International Classification of Childhood Cancer - Third Edition; CNS, central nervous system; LCH, langerhans cell histiocytosis; n, number; SD, standard deviation.

Methods

Impact of event scale – Revised

Psychische Belastungsfolgen

Denken Sie bitte an ein für Sie extrem belastendes Ereignis:

(bitte eintragen)

Wann hat sich dieses ereignet? Monat: _____ Jahr: _____

36. Geben Sie im Folgenden an, wie stark Sie in der vergangenen Woche von diesem Ereignis beeinflusst worden sind. Kreuzen Sie für jede der folgenden Reaktionen an, wie häufig diese bei Ihnen aufgetreten sind.

22 items total

- Intrusion
- Arousal
- Avoidance

- 1. Immer wenn ich an das Ereignis erinnert wurde, kehrten die Gefühle wieder. 0 1 3 5
- 2. Ich hatte Schwierigkeiten, nachts durchzuschlafen. 0 1 3 5
- 5. Ich versuchte mich nicht aufzuregen, wenn ich daran dachte oder daran erinnert wurde. 0 1 3 5

Überhaupt nicht
Selten
Manchmal
Oft

Horowitz, Wilner, & Alvarez, 1979; Maercker & Schützwohl, 1998

Characteristics	Comparison-Parents n=391		CCS-Parents n=663		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age at study *	61.8	8.0	62.1	6.8	0.239
	n	%	n	%	p-value
Sex					0.562
Female	230	58.8	402	60.6	
Male	161	41.2	261	39.4	
Language					0.349
German	278	71.1	489	73.8	
French or Italian	113	28.9	174	26.2	
Migration background *					0.130
No	325	83.1	548	86.6	
Yes	66	16.9	85	13.4	
Education *					0.258
Compulsory schooling	33	9.0	77	12.4	
Vocational training	200	54.5	326	52.5	
Upper secondary or University Degree	134	36.5	218	35.1	
Employed *					0.005
Yes	189	49.0	377	57.9	
No	197	51.0	274	42.1	
Partnership *					0.004
Yes	324	83.9	583	90.0	
No	62	16.1	65	10.0	
Chronic Condition *					0.041
Yes	202	52.2	298	45.6	
No	185	47.8	365	54.4	
Number of children *					<0.001
<2	62	15.9	24	3.9	
≥2	329	84.1	600	96.1	
Child chronic illness *					<0.001
Yes	97	25.0	133	50.2	
No	291	75.0	132	49.8	

Abbreviations: CCS, Childhood Cancer Survivor

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Category	Swiss General Population		Comparison Parents		CCS Parents		Example
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Illness or injury	151	37.6	41	56.5	290	44.4	Lung cancer
Surgery	32	12.2	18	16.7	8	2.4	Knee surgery
Psychological health	39	14.9	16	14.8	17	5.2	Depression
Procreation	22	8.4	2	1.9	6	1.8	Living birth
General Health & Well-being	18	6.9	11	10.2	7	2.1	Sleeplessness
Accident							
Serious accident	36	78.3	14	77.8	8	57.1	Father's accident (broken back)
Transportation accident	10	21.7	4	22.2	6	42.9	Boysie accident
Bereavement							
Sudden violent death	20	8.7	6	6.0	13	13.3	Suicide
Sudden accidental death	7	3.0	5	5.0	1	1.0	Firefighting operation with death
Death	204	88.3	89	89.0	84	85.7	Death of spouse
Relationship							
Couple	108	61.0	99	70.9	32	50.0	Divorce
Children	8	4.5	0	1.0	12	18.8	Kids are unhappy
Family	25	14.1	12	21.8	4	6.3	Being single parent
Friends	10	5.7	3	5.5	3	4.7	Loss of a friendship
Social Interaction	26	14.7	1	1.8	13	20.3	Promise not held
Work/Education							
Education	49	25.7	8	15.1	8	11.9	School-related decisions
Work	125	65.5	42	79.3	54	80.6	Work strain
Finances	13	6.8	5	7.5	5	7.5	Compilation of taxes
Military service	4	2.1	1	1.8	0	0.0	Recruiting school
Other							
Assault with weapon	1	1.3	1	3.6	0	0.0	Terrorist attacks
Captivity	2	2.7	2	7.1	0	0.0	Prison
Combat or exposure to war zone	4	5.3	0	0.0	1	5.3	War
Fire or explosion	4	5.3	1	3.6	1	5.3	Fire at parents' place
Natural disaster	4	5.3	3	10.7	1	5.3	Earthquake
Physical assault	12	16.0	6	21.4	1	5.3	Physical aggression of my son
Sexual assault	8	9.0	4	5.0	2	10.5	Rape
Severe human suffering	1	1.3	1	3.6	0	0.0	Refugees
Serious injury, harm, or death you caused to someone else	2	2.7	1	3.6	0	0.0	Run over elderly women by car
Theft	2	2.7	0	0.0	1	5.3	Theft
Moving house	12	16.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	Moving to Switzerland
Politics	2	2.7	1	3.6	1	5.3	Presidential elections USA
Other specific events	28	29.0	8	9.0	11	57.9	Delivery of an item reported

Note: Categories shaded in light blue according to the Post-traumatic Stress Disorder checklist (Weathers et al., 2013), other categories added by the authors.

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Aim iii
Characteristics associated with PTSS in parents of CCS

- Socio-demographic & Psycho-social
 - Sex
 - Age
 - Education
 - Employment
 - Migration background
 - Questionnaire language
 - Number of children
 - Partner yes/no
- Cancer-related
 - Cancer diagnosis
 - Time since diagnosis
 - Age at diagnosis
 - Therapy type
 - Relapse
 - Survivor age at study
 - Survivor sex
- Event related
 - Type of event
 - Time since event

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